

TACTIC

TOOLS, METHODS AND TRAINING FOR COMMUNITIES
AND SOCIETY TO BETTER PREPARE FOR A CRISIS

Report on the participatory self-assessments for communities

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Document Information

Title	First draft version of the community audit
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Distribution	Public
Document Reference	D2.1
Due Date of the Deliverable	31.03.16

Document History

Date	Revision	Prepared by	Organisation	Approved by	Notes
02.12.15	Version 1.0	Annemarie Müller	UFZ		
	Version 2.0		METU	Nuray Karanci, Canay Dogulu, Serife Yilmaz,	Review, additions
			UFZ	Chloe Begg, Christian Kuhlicke	review
			TRI	Susan Anson Hayley Watson Kush Wadhwa	Review, additions
			ED	Alkiviadis Giannakoulis	additions
			IMGW	Roman Konieczny Tomasz Walczykiewicz	review
			UoN	Cheney Shreve	additions
30/04/16	Version 3.0	Christian Kuhlicke	UFZ		

Acknowledgement

The work described in this publication was supported by the European Union (European Commission, FP7, grant agreement number: 608058).

Table of Content

Table of Content.....	3
1 Introduction.....	5
2 Aims of the self-assessments.....	7
2.1. Organisational self-assessment.....	7
2.2. General public’s self-assessment.....	8
3 Structure of the self-assessment tool.....	9
3.1. Organisational self-assessment (Part 1).....	9
3.2. General public self-assessment (Part 2).....	10
3.3. Results of the self-assessment and linking both self-assessments.....	12
4 Guideline for users.....	12
5 Feedback from the first round of workshops.....	13
6 Feedback from the second round of workshops.....	17
7 Final version of the Self-Assessments.....	18
7.1. The organisational self-assessment - OSA.....	18
7.2. The GPSA.....	59
In comparison to the OSA, only a few adjustments were made to the GPSA.....	59
References.....	102
Appendix.....	105

Preamble

The overall aim of the **TACTIC** project is to increase preparedness to large-scale and cross-border disasters amongst communities and societies in Europe. Therefore TACTIC based its work on the state-of-the-art literature related to risk perception and preparedness, developed a self-assessment both for organisations responsible for managing such different risks as flooding, earthquakes, terrorism and epidemics as well as the general public exposed to these hazards. It also created a catalogue of good practices in education and communication. Rather than taking a top-down approach to preparedness, TACTIC pursues a collaborative project strategy by including different user and stakeholder groups in the development, testing and validation of tools and materials throughout the project by conducting four case studies focusing on terrorism, floods, pandemics and earthquakes. This ensures that the outcomes of the project reflects the needs of end users and ensures that the project's outcomes have a life span after the project has officially ended.

All these findings and outputs are presented in an online learning platform which aims to ensure the sustainability of the use of the projects outcomes after the project has come to an end.

The online platform can be accessed by following this link: <https://www.tacticproject.eu/tosap/>

This document provides the final draft of the self-assessment that was developed in WP (Work Package) 2.

Note: In this document the term “self-assessment” is used to describe the questionnaires developed in WP2. This term replaces the term “audit” which was used in the proposal of the project and early deliverables. The reason for this change is that, as the project has developed so too has our understanding of what the outcomes of the project can and should be. Therefore, rather than developing an independent assessment conducted by a third party, the questionnaire developed within the **TACTIC** project aims to encourage organisations and members of the community to assess their own preparedness. Therefore, members of the project's consortium have agreed that the term “self-assessment” is more appropriate and will be used henceforth.

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1 Introduction

TACTIC believes that strategic risk communication between organisations and the general public can significantly increase disaster preparedness on community level and reduce disaster-related losses.

TACTIC employs the UNISDR definition of preparedness:

“The **knowledge and capacities** developed by governments, professional response and recovery organizations, communities and individuals to effectively **anticipate, respond** to, and **recover** from the impacts of likely, imminent or current **hazard** events or conditions.” (UNISDR, 2007).

This definition emphasises the importance of knowledge and capacities gathered by all involved parties, officials and laypeople. Knowledge, however, is only helpful if it's being validated, spread, updated, and applied in practice. The framework of risk communication focuses on sharing knowledge before, during, and after emergencies with the ultimate aim to increase disaster preparedness.

TACTIC understands risk communication as the exchange of risk-related information between all interested parties (Covello et al. 1987). Interested parties in this case are organisations charged with responsibilities in disaster risk management and the general public, i.e. potentially affected individuals. Risk communication also refers to the tools and methods (including education and training) used to transmit information between those charged with managing risks and hazards (organisations) and those who are at risk (general public).

TACTIC proposes that risk communication should focus on four aims:

- **Raising risk awareness** (e.g. providing information about a hazard and its consequences) (Renn, 1991; Reynolds and Seeger, 2005)
- **Strengthening capacities to act** (e.g. providing the audience with specific preventative and mitigative actions to increase preparedness and to prevent an incident from occurring (e.g. terrorism)) (Renn, 1991, Hagemeyer-Klose and Wagner, 2009; Mileti and Fitzpatrick, 1992; Reynolds and Seeger, 2005)
- **Warning in case of emergency** (e.g. providing clear and timely information about the hazard in an emergency and guidance for actions) (Renn, 1991; Reynolds and Seeger, 2005)
- **Resolving conflicts and building trust** (e.g. key elements of any successful communications strategy which involves discussing different expectations in disaster risk management, etc.) (Glik, 2007; Mileti and Fitzpatrick, 1992; Reynolds and Seeger, 2005)

While the relevance of these four aims was agreed upon by **TACTIC**'s practical case study partners (PCSPs) during the case study workshops, it was highlighted that uncertainties exist regarding the use of appropriate communication methods and contents and that feedback from the intended audience (in this case the general public) is largely missing. So, institutions actively communicate risk-related information covering these four aims, but they are not sure, if their communication efforts serve the desired purpose.

Quite often the effectiveness of an organisation's risk communication becomes only apparent during events when people are forced to respond to the crisis and when knowledge gaps or the lack of preparatory actions become obvious. While valuable lessons regarding risk communication can be

learnt at that stage, the goal should be to improve preparedness as early as possible to prepare the general public and the organisation itself for an event.

Douglas Paton and colleagues (2013) developed the community engagement theory which states that: “The more citizens are able to collectively formulate their risk management needs and strategies and the more they perceive their needs as having been met through their relationship with civic agencies, the more likely they are to trust them and the information they provide, and to use information to decide to adopt hazard preparation measures.” (Paton et al. 2013:30).

Therefore, **TACTIC** developed an Online Self-Assessment Platform (TOSAP) to support the development and the evaluation of a structured communication strategy for organisations on communal level charged with responsibilities in disaster risk management. This tool, however, can only be helpful if it also explicitly addresses the general public as recipient of information that (i) can provided feedback which supports the development/improvement of an organisation’s communication strategy, and (ii) evaluates the current status of risk preparedness and preparedness-related knowledge of the general public (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Components of the TACTIC Online Self-Assessment Platform (TOSAP).

TOSAP consists of several components, such as the self-assessments for organisations and the general public designed as questionnaires, feedback reports, and a library of good practices. D8.1 provides a

preliminary, but detailed description of all components. This deliverable, D8.2, provides an update of the original report in order to provide an overview of the process of finalising the self-assessments.

TOSAP draws on state-of-the-art research as well as the experiences of organisations and the general public with experience of risk management and communication in practice. The self-assessments as first central part of the entire platform were developed and tested in four case studies: floods, earthquakes, epidemics/pandemics, and terrorism.

This report places emphasis on the self-assessments for organisations and the general public that were developed with the aim to ask users about their current status of risk communication activities (organisations) and their communication habits and risk-related knowledge (general public).

This document provides an overview of the aims of the self-assessment tools (Section 2). The reader is then introduced to the structure of the self-assessments (Section 3) and the guidelines for users (Section 4). This first version of the self-assessments was presented in the first round of case study workshops. The feedback obtained in the case studies is presented in section 5. Based on this feedback, an improved version of the self-assessments was developed and tested as an online version during the second round of workshops. The feedback from the second round of workshops is presented in section 6. In a final step, the feedback from the workshops was used to finalise the self-assessments that now appear in the TOSAP. The self-assessments are presented in section 7.

2 Aims of the self-assessments

This section explains how both self-assessments were designed in terms of their content.

The first year of the project included literature reviews (D1.1., D2.1, and D3.1) and the first round of case study workshops for each of the four case studies together with representatives from a range of organisations such as risk and disaster management agencies, municipalities and cities, non-governmental organisations but also businesses (D11.5).

During this first project year, scientific knowledge was collected, analysed and implemented in a first draft version of the community self-assessment (compare D2.1). This draft version was presented to and discussed with the PCSPs during the first round of case study workshops that took place in the case study areas in February and March 2015. One aim of the workshops was to obtain information on existing and functioning communication practices applied in risk management. Another goal was to receive feedback on the content, usefulness and gaps of the preliminary self-assessments (see D11.5). This feedback and the insights gained during the workshop and further literature studies were used to further develop the contents and structure of the self-assessment as it is presented below.

2.1. Organisational self-assessment

The aim of the organisational self-assessment (OSA) is to encourage the evaluation and revision of an organisation's risk communication strategy in terms of suitability and effectiveness. The description of strengths and weaknesses thereby supports the closing of existing communication gaps between organisations and the general public and the improvement of disaster risk preparedness. Furthermore, the aim is to provide scientific guidance and expertise which will enable organisations to develop place-based and demand-oriented communication practices.

The following risk communication strategy structure has been adapted from the EPA (2012), and is used as the structure of the short and long feedback reports for the OSA:

1. **Context** of the organisation's work conditions and its risk communication practices
2. Current **aim(s) of** risk communication activities
3. **Intended audience**
4. **Contents and key messages**
5. Choice of **communication method**
6. **Barriers and good aspects** of risk communication

In regards to the specific focus of the OSA, the following central questions and aims have been identified:

- What are the context-related conditions like that determine risk communication?
- Who communicates what, how and to whom?
- Who should communicate what, how and to whom?
- Which communication barriers need to be considered?
- How can the existing risk communication strategy be improved or refined?

2.2. General public's self-assessment

The general public's self-assessment (GPSA) aims to improve the disaster preparedness of individuals and to encourage them to actively search for further risk-related information. The types of information they may require in order to become better prepared has been outlined in D3.1., the components of preparedness (e.g. knowledge/information, motivation, resources, networks and responsibility) have been identified as important factors that need to be addressed to ensure the preparedness of the general public. These components have been taken into account in the structuring of the GPSA.

Specifically, the GPSA has three aims: 1) to provide feedback in regards to current practices of risk communication in their community in order to assist in the improvement of an organisation's communications strategy by providing feedback to organisations interested in developing/improving their risk communication, 2) to assess individual risk knowledge and knowledge gaps, risk communication needs, preferred and trusted risk communication tools/channels, and other factors that might determine whether an individual takes preparedness measures or not according to the model developed by Becker et al. (2012). This information can be used to improve scientific understandings of preparedness and 3) to assess and provide members of the general public with feedback in regards to their own risk preparedness.

In regards to the specific focus of the **general public's self-assessment**, the following central questions and aims have been identified:

- Which risk-relevant knowledge is available among to general public?
- Which communication channels (e.g. radio, internet, flyer, etc.) are accepted and used?
- What type and content of communication works well and is useful?

- What motivates individuals to follow suggestions and to take preparedness actions?
- What should/could be improved in order to increase risk preparedness?
- What is the level of preparedness among the general public in a community?

All stages of the disaster risk management cycle, mitigation and preparedness (before), response (during) and recovery/reconstruction (after) are addressed in both parts of the self-assessment tool.

3 Structure of the self-assessment tool

By using the Online Learning Platform (<http://moodle.com/>) we were able to create one tool with two different user interfaces, one for the general public and one for organisations (see Figure 2). For one part, the system works like a virtual class room: students (i.e. the general public) answer their questions showing what risk-relevant information they have, how they receive it, how they use it as a decision making aid, what else they would need/like to know and what motivates them to take preparedness actions, how prepared they feel. The teacher (i.e. the organisations) receives the feedback and can use it, in additions to the results of the organisation’s self-assessment, for further decision making processes and planning/adaptation of their risk communication strategy. The answer to each student’s question will be saved in the Moodle system. The individual and overall statistics of the answers given can then be accessed by the organisation (“teacher”). The organisations are not just teachers that have access to the answers provided by the general public. Therefore, the system provides organisations with the possibility to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of their communication strategy.

Answers to the questions in the platform will provide content for feedback reports for the organisations and the general public as well as links to the library of “good” practices which provides organisations with inspiration in the development of their communications strategy and provides the general public with examples of practices which aim to fill their identified information needs. The self-assessment tool questions and the good practices need to be combined using a categorisation mechanism (compare D3.2, and D8.1).

The following sub-sections focus on the structure of each of the self-assessments in turn.

3.1. Organisational self-assessment (Part 1)

The organisational assessment is a questionnaire that contains questions related to:

1. the analysis of the organisation’s working context and
2. the analysis of the existing communication strategy/activities.

Closed questions with pre-defined answers are asked to obtain information that help assessing the five components of preparedness and the current status of the risk communication strategy:

The role of the contextual analysis: the contextual analysis asks for the hazard experience within the community, the availability of an organisation’s resources that can be spent on risk communication activities, it asks about the networks that an organisation has established and works with and about responsibilities and aims of risk communication.

The role of the assessment of the risk communication strategy: This part basically covers all steps that should be contained in a risk communication strategy (compare Section 2.1). In other words, it puts a focus on the strategic exchange of risk-related information as central measure to increase a community's preparedness.

We are asking different kinds of questions in the self-assessments. Some of these questions are informative for the organisation and want to encourage the user to reflect on risk communication or context variables without providing further information for the user. Other questions function as a link to the library of good practices: The answers to these questions are displayed at the end of the assessment tool in a feedback report (compare D8.1). The user of the platform can then decide about which practices he or she would like to learn more about, i.e. how the filter for the library of good practices (upper right part of Figure 2) should look like. If the assessment for example reveals that nothing is done to rebuild trust after an event so far, the user could choose to learn about practices that aim at rebuilding trust after catastrophes.

The organisational self-assessment process ends with (i) an analysis and presentation of **the analysis of the existing risk communication strategy** (are risk communication goals achieved= how can risk communication be improved in terms of methods and additional communication goals?) and with (ii) an analysis of **context-specific variables**, such as the availability of resources, hazard-specific questions and (iii) the agreement on aims to increase preparedness based on the presentation of results. This is the basis for the feedback report and selection and recommendation of practices from the library of good practices with the assumption that preparedness is a process and therefore something that can always be improved upon.

3.2. General public self-assessment (Part 2)

The GPSA is designed in a comparable way to the OSA but it contains fewer questions. In the GPSA, each participant receives a direct feedback with additional advice.

The preparedness check is based on an assessment approach developed with regard to earthquakes, but was meanwhile also applied to other hazards (Becker et al., 2012; Paton, 2003; Paton, 2007; Paton, 2008; Paton et al., 2015; Paton et al., 2008; Paton and Johnston, 2001; Paton et al., 2000). The model has a very high explanatory power with regard to explaining preparedness actions before, during and after a crises event (see also Shreve et al., 2014) and is one of the best tested and most widely applied behavior-related models in hazard and risk research. More specifically, Figure 14 outlines the model and how the different components underlying the preparedness model are interlinked. The single components (i.e. information & knowledge, immediate outcomes, beliefs and feelings, community and trust as well as responsibility and community) are detailed in more depth in subsequent sections.

Figure 2: The model underlying the general public self-assessment

Source: Based on Becker et al., 2012

3.3. Results of the self-assessment and linking both self-assessments

The result of organisation's self-assessment is a **feedback report** (see Deliverable 3.2 for more details). The feedback report contains those issues that were identified as gaps during the assessment, For example. If the user stated that raising awareness for the hazard is not part of the current communication strategy the feedback report will provide information to the organisation in regards to whether the methods of communication that they use are suitable in order to reach that aim. In addition, a link to the library of good practices will be provided. For example, the feedback report will contain the following statement: "If you would like to see examples of how to raise hazard awareness, please click [HERE]". The user can then click on the link provided and will be directed to the library of good practices. In this database, the user will find a selection of all practices in the database that contain the label "risk communication aim: raising awareness". The user can click through the practices and the user can modify the search results by activating further selection criteria such as hazard type, language of the practice, intended audience, etc. (see D3.2.) for more information on the categorisation and selection criteria.

Two feedback reports have been developed for the organisations: 1) a short feedback report which automatically responds to the answers that the organisation provides in the OSA, and 2) a long feedback report which is a detailed but static report which provides information about each of the steps of a communications strategy based on the possible answers to the OSA and is available as a PDF resource. The general public will receive a shorter feedback which focuses on the assessment outcomes and provides feedback on relevant factors that shape individual preparedness as well as helpful links to external websites.

4 Guideline for users

To increase the user friendliness and to explain the added value, the self-assessment tool starts with a short introduction containing a brief outlines on the single steps:

- 1 What is expected from you?** In this first part the user is asked to evaluate its existing communication strategy and the applied methods, to reflect about the current status and to unravel potential for optimization.
- 2 How does the process work?** The methodological design of the tool is explained here. The user will need to respond to questions with pre-defined answers, this means that he/she is not required to enter free text. The tool will be accessible online and can be conducted alone or in a group.
- 3 What will be the result?** The result of the self-assessment process for organisations is an evaluation of the existing risk communication strategy, the suggestions of alternative practices and methods, and (if this feature is advertised and used) feedback from the population on the existing risk communication methods and potential additional requirements. The result for the general public is a suggestion of links to obtain further information and it also has an educational value.

The user can also access the overarching Deliverable 8.2 and learn more about the overarching idea of social learning and how this is linked to risk communication and community preparedness and the single assessments..

5 Feedback from the first round of workshops

The self-assessments have so far been developed by drawing on the findings of WP1 and on additional literature research (scientific and grey literature). The organisation's self-assessment was in its first version validated and adapted during the case study workshops where organisations such as NGOs as well as experts and authorities involved in disaster risk management and members of the public participated. The first round of workshops took place in February and March 2015. Feedback covering one or more of the following points was collected in each case study workshop:

- The usefulness of a preparedness self-assessment tool in general
- The general structure of the self-assessment tool
- The requirements/features that increase the likelihood of its practical implementation (number and content of questions, format of presentation, presentation of results, number of good practices suggested, duration of the self-assessment process, technical limitations, documentation, terminology used, etc.)
- The content and ordering of the questions
- The usefulness/completeness of aspects covered
- “no-go” questions
- Usefulness of feedback from the general public (usefulness of sharing the results from the general public's self-assessment tool in some way)
- Advice on how the self-assessment tool could be advertised
- Advice on the target audience
- Recommendations on how and when to test the self-assessment tool (e.g. contacts to potential users, also individuals)
- General strengths and weaknesses.

The findings from the different case studies were different in each case study.

During the **terrorism** workshop, participants recommended that the user/s of the self-assessment tool need to be more clearly defined as the particular user will influence its framing. Therefore, it was suggested to add a filter question to help people to decide which part of the self-assessment they should complete. Participants discussed how the self-assessment tool could be more useful to businesses and NGOs rather than for governments in regards to terrorism. This is likely to be because in London, businesses are prepared as part of the wider community. As the self-assessment focuses only on communication, participants questioned how we know how the public interpreted the message and whether people are prepared or took action. It was proposed to not only improve communication but also to provide information about what actions could be undertaken to improve preparedness (e.g., content of the communication practice). In terms of the motivation of potential users there is the need to provide people with an incentive to complete the self-assessment and contextualise why they should complete it. Some questions were highlighted as being organisational specific and if not relevant to a specific organisation would be based on personal opinion. An interviewee expressed concern over the potential for mixed messaging in terms of what is delivered by

the self-assessment and what they are able to do. They are unable to prescribe one guidance or route to follow and as an organisation, they have to stay within their remit and expertise. Additional feedback included shortening the length of the self-assessment, editing the content and considering the terminology used and re-evaluating the use of the “don’t know” response option.

In the **floods** workshop, there was a large interest in a scientific support for the choice of appropriate communication methods or for flood risk measures in general. It was emphasized by participants both from municipalities and specialists in disaster management that science-based policy and action recommendations would be really helpful as a support for actions to be taken and decisions to be made, in particular if those have to be agreed upon with superior authorities. That is a strong support of the development of the self-assessment tool, which would give guidance on the choice of appropriate communication methods to reach a goal under given framework conditions (such as available resources and specific target audiences). Another aspect that was valued it that the self-assessment tool will also deliver feedback from the target audiences (i.e. the general public) on how risk communication should be designed. Most participants have a range of communication tools established but they are still not sure if they meet the needs of their target audiences and what they could do to improve the efficiency and usefulness of their risk communication strategy. That means that we need to design the general public’s self-assessment in such a way that it delivers information on specific requirements and desires of the target audiences.

In the workshop on **earthquakes** participants generally seemed to be keen to use the platform to increase preparedness of Kaynaşlı to earthquakes and other hazards. The most pronounced feedback concerned internet use in Kaynaşlı, particularly, the limitations in the access to the internet in some segments of the public (e.g., elderly and citizens with low levels of education may have limited access), as a factor that might hinder the use of the platform. In Kaynaşlı, about 70% of the households have Internet access, so enabling those who do not use Internet to be involved in the assessment and the practices seems to be an important consideration for the project. A user training guide for the technical operation of the platform was also suggested to promote the use of the platform. Furthermore, the suggestions centered around the need for a simple and easy presentation of the self-assessment tool. The main focus of the feedback provided by the participants on increasing the use of the self-assessment was on the ‘design’. Participants stated that the self-assessment should be short, focused and understandable, supported by visual aids, and should be accessible and easy to access, and also user-friendly. Different user interfaces for specific target audiences (e.g., more attractive user face for children use), need for ‘technical responsible bodies’ in the long run, and translation of other countries’ practices on different hazards were among the other criticisms and concerns that were raised. A final concern was about the good practices and the need to evaluate and comment on the available practices by the users rather than taking them as good examples in all respects.

In the case of **epidemics/pandemics**, participants were supportive of the idea of the self-assessment and online platform, especially as it was viewed as creating an opportunity to stimulate discussion regarding the effectiveness and practicality of different preparedness measures. Bio-security is the general term used to refer to disease preparedness measures on the farm, primarily related to cleaning and disinfecting potentially infected premises/animals. Many of the bio-security measures recommended to the community during the 2001 foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) epidemic were viewed as untested and exhaustive which created a feeling of mistrust. For example, residents were asked to scrub down and disinfect vehicles, as well as highways/roads near their farms to reduce the

risk of disease spread via vehicles going to and from farms. Additionally, businesses were contracted to do cleaning and disinfectant (C&D) during various stages of the crisis by the government. The businesses hired, as well as the selection process, were sometimes viewed as ad hoc and ineffective. Often times farmers had to pay for these C&D measures, but were not involved in the selection process. There needs to be more clear information regarding what bio-security and preparedness measures are more effective for farmers to be engaged in and when outside organisations/actors should be involved in. Incorporating this into the self-assessment, as a ranking criteria or context note, would be useful.

The term 'bio-security' was not viewed as widespread prior to the 2001 FMD epidemic, but it is now far more common, however it is still viewed that government and other agencies primarily tasked with disease control need to do more with regards to testing and evaluating the effectiveness and potential environmental impacts of different bio-security measures. One challenge then, is that this information may not be readily available to inform the self-assessment. However, there is also an opportunity to start this discussion through the self-assessment, e.g. by having questions asking if knowledge/information on the effectiveness/efficiency of different bio-security or other preparedness measures is an obstacle or concern for preparedness on the general public's self-assessment could alert organisations or practitioners tasked with preparedness that this is a potential gap to address and that it is a community priority. The platform can also raise awareness of different preparedness interventions, actors or networks to contact during a crisis, which was also viewed as a challenge during the 2001 FMD epidemic.

Other specific challenges for epidemics/pandemics self-assessment emerged as the need make clear distinctions between guidelines that pertain to animal diseases versus human diseases. While there is some clear overlap in preparedness strategies between human and animal diseases, e.g. quarantine, vaccination, hand washing, etc. are common preparedness strategies for both human/animal diseases, the context is very different at the household level. Farmers, for instance, might be more inclined to take both the organisational preparedness self-assessment, as they are largely responsible for bio-security and other preparedness measures to reduce disease risk on the farm, as well as the general public's self-assessment for personal/family preparedness. Individuals not engaged in farming, however, would not need detailed information on bio-security, but could benefit from general community guidelines, e.g. how to reduce disease risk for farmers as a community member/non-farmer. This could perhaps be addressed by having a different profile for users to select for the self-assessment.

Transfer of knowledge/information of the natural practice of the farming community (e.g. density of animals, volume, timing and direction of trade of livestock, concerns relating to seasonality and animal welfare, etc.) by farmers to risk managers was a key challenge during the 2001 FMD epidemic. Knowledge/information about the natural practice of the farming community is essential for effective disease control during an epidemic/pandemic. Therefore, it was recommended that the online platform should have an outlet, function, or a forum for individuals, informal organisations, or other community groups to identify or volunteer relevant risk information or needs. Community knowledge/information isn't necessarily fully captured by risk management organisations/practitioners and thus, it may not be possible to reflect the importance of this in self-assessment questions. One way to address this challenge might be to have a thread or a forum on 'lessons learnt' and 'lessons to be learnt' in the online platform. Another concern was ensuring that the individual/community self-assessment was brief and interactive, as it was viewed that people would not want to spend too much

time on an assessment, but a short, interactive version aimed to peak interest might motivate people to engage more with the “good practices” library.

The final self-assessments tool will particularly focus on low-risk/high-impact scenarios and will include possible cascading effects and cross-border implications. The starting point, however, was the development of a case study specific single-hazard tool that will be extended in the second year of the project to cover multiple hazards, cascading effects, and cross-border implications. It will also be available in all case-study languages (German, English, Polish, and Turkish). This first draft of the organisation’s self-assessment tool was discussed with the potential users in the case study workshop. The generally very positive feedback is now being implemented in the tool.

The second half of the project will then be the extension to a multi-hazard self-assessment that will again be presented and discussed with multiple stakeholders in the second round of the case study workshops taking place at the end of 2015.

The general public’s self-assessment tool will be further developed in parallel.

Additionally, some more specific questions will be answered within the second year of the project. The first concerns the presentation of the results of the organisation’s self-assessment. So far, we are providing a feedback form that contains information related to questions about the risk communication strategy only, more precisely on the deficits. We would like to extend that to a full feedback containing both positive and negative aspects that also contains more information on why the aims are so important and how methods can be best selected. We are also thinking about a suitable way of including the results from the contextual analysis in such a way that they are helpful and motivating for the organisation even if the context conditions indicate very limited room for improvement of the existing communication efforts (e.g. because of low resource availability and/or a lack of responsibility for communicating risks).

We are furthermore going to improve and link the questions concerning the risk communication strategy within the organisational self-assessment. Questions on which methods are best suited for communicating which aim and for reaching which target audience will be further elaborated and connected in such a way that the feedback can be provided in a more precise and efficient way. Questions will comprise issues such as: Which methods do you use for communicating a certain aim (e.g. raising awareness)? Who is your target audience for that? Do you have specific methods for specific target audiences? Etc.

Next to the improvement of the general public’s self-assessment that we are working on, we are discussing several options of presenting the results in such a way that it is both encouraging people to spend more time learning about the risks, to share their knowledge, and to actively prepare for risks.

As the results of the general public’s self-assessment is also functioning as input for the organisations (feedback on their strategy), we are elaborating filter mechanisms that help organisations filtering the answers of the general public according to their needs (e.g. only certain age groups).

For the presentation of the first version of the OSA and the GPSA please see D2.1.

6 Feedback from the second round of workshops

Based on the first round of workshops the self-assessments were updated and improved. In preparation for the second round of workshops, TACTIC implemented the self-assessments into the TOSAP. The aim of the workshops was to gain an impression of the functionality and quality of the content of the self-assessments. Both the OSA and GPSA were tested. The following section presents the overall feedback that was received as a result of the workshops.

General points

- **Overall length of the assessment and the feedback reports was considered as problematic.**
 - o *We shortened the questionnaire substantially and have excluded questions that are not directly relevant for the assessment and the feedback. We will also indicate at the beginning how long the assessment will take. Additionally, we propose to also have a shorter version of the feedback report which will be linked to the goals, methods etc. section and which will be more dynamic; it will provide positive feedback based on the answers provided. Additionally, we will have a longer report that contains all the relevant information the assessment is based on; it will be static generated independent of the results of the assessment and will explicate that relevance of all questions asked in the assessments, provide more information and links to the library of good practices. We might include a progress bar.*
- **Purpose of tool, structure of the assessment as well as what kind of feedback to expect needs to become clearer in the intro section.** Respondents need to understand how the self-assessment is structured, how it works (e.g. screen shot, short video), what kind of feedback they can expect (see above) and what they can learn from the assessment and what not.
 - o *Each part of the TOSAP will be introduced by a text explaining the importance of the section and what the user can expect.*
- **Simplify questions and language.** There was an overall impression that many questions were too technical, too long, not to the point etc.
 - o *We have taken care to reduce the use of technical language. We will also take care to insure that the self-assessments are translated into each of the case study languages.*
- **Guiding through the assessment.**
 - o *We have developed short paragraphs that held users to be guided through the assessment.*

Specific thematic points:

- **Different communications aims.** It was hard for respondents to understand that they are answering questions related to different communication aims. This needs to be clearer throughout the assessment.
 - o *This was made now clearer throughout the assessment*
- **Scaling: Uneven or even scaling?**
 - o *The answer categories are now only "yes/no" in order to enable to linkages to the feedback reports.*
- **Organisations.** The category "organizations" is perceived as begin too broad.
 - o *This category has been simplified; just three categories in the beginning: government body, private company, non-profit organisation and other.*

Technical points:

- **Icons.** Not only text, but also icons should be included in order to ensure better guidance.
 - o *A graphic designer has developed icons and colour schemes for the TOSAP*
- **Anonymous login/**registration without email address was desired for the general public. Workshop participants were concerned that a formal login would very likely decrease the general public's motivation to conduct the self-assessment.
 - o *A short text which explains why this information is important and that it will not be used by third parties has been provided.*
- **Linking results of the GPSA with organisations responsible**
 - o *This is still an area that needs improvements, as in its current set up, this can not be done automatically. However, if ED or UFZ are contacted directly, we will be able to set up an account that allows the direct feedback within one community*
- **Should the TOSAP be available as a mobile app?**
 - o *It is acknowledged that this is a good idea and could be pursued in the future but it is not something that **TACTIC** will be able to produce within the scope of this project.*

More specific feedback in regards to specific questions and how they have been dealt with in the updated version of the self-assessments can be found in D11.7

7 Final version of the Self-Assessments

This section presents the final versions of both OSA and the GPSA in turn.

7.1. The organisational self-assessment - OSA

The final version of the OSA includes some important changes to the original version of the self-assessment. For example, it was decided that not all questions were suitable for all case studies. This is why we have deleted warning from the earthquakes self-assessment. We did so because we acknowledge that it is not possible to warn the general public during an earthquake. In addition some of the questions relate to risk perception (e.g. outrage factors) as well as the question related to the benefits of taking action have been removed from the terrorism self-assessment.

11	Terrorism	Floods	Epidemics	Earthquakes
	<p>Welcome to the TACTIC Self-Assessment on “Terrorism” for Organisations!</p> <p>Do you want to know how well you are communicating with the public? Do you want to have a feedback on your risk communication practices? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 20 to 30 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>We will ask you, among others, about your working context, about the goals you want to achieve with your risk communication activities and what methods you use.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a feedback report will be generated. This report gives you an overview about strengths and potentials of your organisation’s risk communication strategy. In addition, we will link you to our TACTIC Library of good practices and provide you with specific examples that can be inspiring and</p>	<p>Welcome to the TACTIC Self-Assessment on “Floods” for Organisations!</p> <p>Do you want to know how well you are communicating with the public? Do you want to have a feedback on your risk communication practices? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 20 to 30 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>We will ask you, among others, about your working context, about the goals you want to achieve with your risk communication activities and what methods you use.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a feedback report will be generated. This report gives you an overview about strengths and potentials of your organisation’s risk communication strategy. In addition, we will link you to our TACTIC Library of good practices and provide you with specific examples that can be inspiring and might be helpful to learn more about how you might improve your communication activities.</p> <p>Of course, you are also free to have a</p>	<p>Welcome to the TACTIC Self-Assessment on “Epidemics” for Organisations!</p> <p>Do you want to know how well you are communicating with the public? Do you want to have a feedback on your risk communication practices? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 20 to 30 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>We will ask you, among others, about your working context, about the goals you want to achieve with your risk communication activities and what methods you use.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a feedback report will be generated. This report gives you an overview about strengths and potentials of your organisation’s risk communication strategy. In addition, we will link you to our TACTIC Library of good practices and provide you with specific examples that can be inspiring and</p>	<p>Welcome to the TACTIC Self-Assessment on “Earthquakes” for Organisations!</p> <p>Do you want to know how well you are communicating with the public? Do you want to have a feedback on your risk communication practices? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 20 to 30 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>We will ask you, among others, about your working context, about the goals you want to achieve with your risk communication activities and what methods you use.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a feedback report will be generated. This report gives you an overview about strengths and potentials of your organisation’s risk communication strategy. In addition, we will link you to our TACTIC Library of good practices and provide you with specific examples that can be inspiring and</p>

	<p>might be helpful to learn more about how you might improve your communication activities.</p> <p>Of course, you are also free to have a look in the TACTIC Library of good practices without conducting the assessment [Link].</p> <p>If you would like to learn more about risk communication after having conducted the assessment, we recommend having a look at the TACTIC Handbook of Social Learning and Risk Communication. This document gives you a detailed overview about general principles of risk communication and provides you with a step-by-step approach which aims in enabling you to develop a long-term risk communication strategy. [Link].</p> <p><i>If you need information about the options, please place the mouse on them. If a question mark appears, you will get more information when you click on it.</i></p>	<p>look in the TACTIC Library of good practices without conducting the assessment [Link].</p> <p>If you would like to learn more about risk communication after having conducted the assessment, we recommend having a look at the TACTIC Handbook of Social Learning and Risk Communication. This document gives you a detailed overview about general principles of risk communication and provides you with a step-by-step approach which aims in enabling you to develop a long-term risk communication strategy. [Link].</p> <p><i>If you need information about the options, please place the mouse on them. If a question mark appears, you will get more information when you click on it.</i></p>	<p>might be helpful to learn more about how you might improve your communication activities.</p> <p>Of course, you are also free to have a look in the TACTIC Library of good practices without conducting the assessment [Link].</p> <p>If you would like to learn more about risk communication after having conducted the assessment, we recommend having a look at the TACTIC Handbook of Social Learning and Risk Communication. This document gives you a detailed overview about general principles of risk communication and provides you with a step-by-step approach which aims in enabling you to develop a long-term risk communication strategy. [Link].</p> <p><i>If you need information about the options, please place the mouse on them. If a question mark appears, you will get more information when you click on it.</i></p>	<p>might be helpful to learn more about how you might improve your communication activities.</p> <p>Of course, you are also free to have a look in the TACTIC Library of good practices without conducting the assessment [Link].</p> <p>If you would like to learn more about risk communication after having conducted the assessment, we recommend having a look at the TACTIC Handbook of Social Learning and Risk Communication. This document gives you a detailed overview about general principles of risk communication and provides you with a step-by-step approach which aims in enabling you to develop a long-term risk communication strategy. [Link].</p> <p><i>If you need information about the options, please place the mouse on them. If a question mark appears, you will get more information when you click on it.</i></p>
1	Where is your organisation located?	Where is your organisation located?	Where is your organisation located?	Where is your organisation located?

2	<p>What type of organisation are you working for?</p> <p>a) Government body b) Private company c) Non-profit organisation d) Other</p>	<p>What type of organisation are you working for?</p> <p>a) Government body b) Private company c) Non-profit organisation d) Others</p>	<p>What type of organisation are you working for?</p> <p>a) Government body b) Private company c) Non-profit organisation d) Others</p>	<p>What type of organisation are you working for?</p> <p>a) Government body b) Private company c) Non-profit organisation d) Others</p>
3	<p>Which hazard do you think is most relevant for your organisation? (first question, 5 buttons)</p> <p>a. Floods b. Earthquakes c. Epidemics (animal- and human-transmitted disease, e.g. mad cow disease and influenza) d. Terrorism</p>	<p>Which hazard do you think is most relevant for your organisation? (first question, 5 buttons)</p> <p>a. Floods b. Earthquakes c. Epidemics (animal- and human-transmitted disease, e.g. mad cow disease and influenza) d. Terrorism</p>	<p>Which hazard do you think is most relevant for your organisation? (first question, 5 buttons)</p> <p>a. Floods b. Earthquakes c. Epidemics (animal- and human-transmitted disease, e.g. mad cow disease and influenza) d. Terrorism</p>	<p>Which hazard do you think is most relevant for your organisation? (first question, 5 buttons)</p> <p>a. Floods b. Earthquakes c. Epidemics (animal- and human-transmitted disease, e.g. mad cow disease and influenza) d. Terrorism</p>
	HAZARD EXPERIENCE AND HAZARD PERCEPTION			

4	<p>Has your community/city/region ever experienced the consequences of a terrorist attack (e.g. disruption to daily life)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (continue with question 9)</p>	<p>Has your community/city/region ever experienced the consequences of a flood event (e.g. disruption to daily life)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (continue with question 9)</p>	<p>Has your community/city/region ever experienced the negative consequences of an epidemic event (e.g. disruption to daily life)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (continue with question 9)</p>	<p>Has your community/city/region ever experienced the negative consequences of an earthquake event? (e.g. disruption to daily life)</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (continue with question 9)</p>
5	<p>If you answered yes to Question 4, when did a terrorist attack last occur in your community?</p> <p>a) Less than one year ago b) Between one and ten years ago c) More than ten years ago</p>	<p>If you answered yes to Question 4, when did a flood event last occur in your community?</p> <p>a) Less than one year ago b) Between one and ten years ago c) More than ten years ago</p>	<p>If you answered yes to Question 4, when did an epidemic event last occur in your community?</p> <p>a) Less than one year ago b) Between one and ten years ago c) More than ten years ago</p>	<p>If you answered yes to Question 4, when did an earthquake event last occur in your community?</p> <p>a) Less than one year ago b) Between one and ten years ago c) More than ten years ago</p>
6	<p>Has your organisation drawn out lessons from the most recent terrorist attack?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Has your organisation drawn out lessons from the most recent flood event?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Has your organisation drawn out lessons from the most recent epidemic event?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Has your organisation drawn out lessons from the most recent earthquake event?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
7	<p>If yes, has your organisation systematically documented these</p>	<p>If yes, has your organisation systematically documented these</p>	<p>If yes, has your organisation systematically documented these</p>	<p>If yes, has your organisation systematically documented these</p>

	<p>lessons and developed for recommendations for improvement?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>lessons and developed for recommendations for improvement?</p> <p>d) Yes e) No f) I don't know</p>	<p>lessons and developed for recommendations for improvement?</p> <p>g) Yes h) No i) I don't know</p>	<p>lessons and developed for recommendations for improvement?</p> <p>j) Yes k) No l) I don't know</p>
8	<p>If yes, have these recommendations been implemented?</p> <p>a) Yes, we have implemented all of our recommendations b) Yes, we have implemented some of the recommendations and are in the process of implementing the others c) We plan to implement our recommendations in the future d) No, we will not implement our recommendations</p>	<p>If yes, have these recommendations been implemented?</p> <p>a) Yes, we have implemented all of our recommendations b) Yes, we have implemented some of the recommendations and are in the process of implementing the others c) We plan to implement our recommendations in the future d) No, we will not implement our recommendations</p>	<p>If yes, have these recommendations been implemented?</p> <p>a) Yes, we have implemented all of our recommendations b) Yes, we have implemented some of the recommendations and are in the process of implementing the others c) We plan to implement our recommendations in the future d) No, we will not implement our recommendations</p>	<p>If yes, have these recommendations been implemented?</p> <p>a) Yes, we have implemented all of our recommendations b) Yes, we have implemented some of the recommendations and are in the process of implementing the others c) We plan to implement our recommendations in the future d) No, we will not implement our recommendations</p>

9	<p>Risks and actions to mitigate risks can be perceived differently (e.g. the organisation may perceive the risk of terrorism as being very low but the general public may believe that it is high). Are you aware of differences in how your organisation perceives the risk of terrorism and how members of the public perceive the risk of terrorism?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Risks and actions to mitigate risks can be perceived differently (e.g. the organisation may believe that it is not possible to create 100% protection against flooding but the general public may believe that it is possible). Are you aware of differences in how your organisation perceives the risk of flooding and how members of the public perceive the risk of flooding?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Risks and actions to mitigate risks can be perceived differently (e.g. the organisation may believe that the risk of an epidemic is very high but the general public may believe that the risk is low). Are you aware of differences in the perception of risk by your organisation/your personal perception of risk and that of members of the public?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Risks and actions to mitigate risks can be perceived differently (e.g. the organisation may believe that human action can reduce the damage that an earthquake causes but the general public may believe that an earthquake is a natural event or an event sent by God and do not believe that human actions can make a difference). Are you aware of differences in the perception of risk by your organisation/your personal perception of risk and that of members of the public?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
10	<p>Did conflicts arise out of differences in risk perception?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No, not yet - but I am sure that conflicts will arise c) No, the difference in risk perception is rather minor d) I don't know</p>	<p>Did conflicts arise out of differences in risk perception?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No, not yet - but I am sure that conflicts will arise c) No, the difference in risk perception is rather minor d) I don't know</p>	<p>Did conflicts arise out of differences in risk perception over epidemics?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No, not yet - but I am sure that conflicts will arise c) No, the difference in risk perception regarding epidemics is rather minor d) I don't know</p>	<p>Did conflicts arise out of differences in risk perception?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No, not yet - but I am sure that conflicts will arise c) No, the difference in risk perception is rather minor d) I don't know</p>

11	We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Much research has highlighted that there is a difference in the way that risk managers and those at risk perceive the given risk. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your opinion and first thoughts.	We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Much research has highlighted that there is a difference in the way that risk managers and those at risk perceive the given risk. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your opinion and first thoughts.	We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Much research has highlighted that there is a difference in the way that risk managers and those at risk perceive the given risk. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your opinion and first thoughts.	We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Much research has highlighted that there is a difference in the way that risk managers and those at risk perceive the given risk. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your opinion and first thoughts.
	<p>To what extent is the risk of terrorism voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of terrorism) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>	<p>To what extent is the risk of flooding voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of flooding) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>	<p>To what extent is the risk of epidemics voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of epidemics) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>	<p>To what extent is the risk of earthquake voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of earthquakes) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>
		<p>To what extend is the risk of flooding natural or human-made?</p> <p>1 natural 2</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of epidemics is natural or human-made?</p> <p>1 natural</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of an earthquake event natural or human-made?</p> <p>1 natural</p>

		3 4 5 human-made	2 3 4 5 human-made	2 3 4 5 human-made
	To what extend is the risk of terrorism threatening or unthreatening? 1 threatening 2 3 4 5 unthreatening	To what extend is the risk of flooding threatening or unthreatening? 1 threatening 2 3 4 5 unthreatening	To what extend is the risk of epidemics threatening or unthreatening? 1 threatening 2 3 4 5 unthreatening	To what extend is the risk of an earthquake event threatening or unthreatening? 1 threatening 2 3 4 5 unthreatening
	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of terrorism? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of flooding? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of epidemics? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of earthquakes? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar
	To what extend is the risk of terrorism manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable	To what extend is risk of flooding manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable	To what extend is the epidemic risk manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable	To what extend is the risk of an earthquake event manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable

		<p>To what extend is the risk of flooding distributed fairly or unfairly among members of society?</p> <p>1 fairly 2 3 4 5 unfairly</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of epidemics distributed fairly or unfairly among members of society?</p> <p>1 fairly 2 3 4 5 unfairly</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of earthquakes distributed fairly or unfairly among members of society?</p> <p>1 fairly 2 3 4 5 unfairly</p>
		<p>To what extend is the knowledge about the community's risk of flooding scientifically certain or uncertain?</p> <p>1 certain 2 3 4 5 uncertain</p>	<p>To what extend is the knowledge about the community's risk of an epidemic event scientifically certain or uncertain?</p> <p>1 certain 2 3 4 5 uncertain</p>	<p>To what extend is the knowledge about the community's risk of an earthquake event scientifically certain or uncertain?</p> <p>1 certain 2 3 4 5 uncertain</p>
12	<p>Does your organisation treat preparedness to terrorism differently to preparedness to other hazards?</p> <p>a) No, preparing for terrorism is not different to preparing for other types of hazards b) Yes, terrorism has unique</p>	<p>Does your organisation treat preparedness to floods differently to preparedness to other hazards?</p> <p>a) No, preparing for floods is not different to preparing for other types of hazards b) Yes, floods has unique characteristics that require particular considerations</p>	<p>Does your organisation treat preparedness to epidemics differently to preparedness to other hazards?</p> <p>a) No, preparing for epidemics is not different to preparing for other types of hazards b) Yes, epidemics has unique</p>	<p>Does your organisation treat preparedness to earthquakes differently to preparedness to other hazards?</p> <p>a) No, preparing for earthquakes is not different to preparing for other types of hazards b) Yes, earthquakes has</p>

	<p>characteristics that require particular considerations</p> <p>c) I am not sure whether this has been considered</p> <p>d) not applicable</p>	<p>c) I am not sure whether this has been considered</p> <p>d) not applicable</p>	<p>characteristics that require particular considerations</p> <p>c) I am not sure whether this has been considered</p> <p>d) not applicable</p>	<p>unique characteristics that require particular considerations</p> <p>c) I am not sure whether this has been considered</p> <p>d) not applicable</p>
13	<p>How often do you collaborate with the following organisations in your day-to-day business? (regularly, from time to time, never)</p> <p>a) public</p> <p>b) private</p> <p>c) public/private</p> <p>d) non-profit</p> <p>e) others</p>	<p>How often do you collaborate with the following organisations in your day-to-day business? (regularly, from time to time, never)</p> <p>a) public</p> <p>b) private</p> <p>c) public/private</p> <p>d) non-profit</p> <p>e) others</p>	<p>How often do you collaborate with the following organisations in your day-to-day business? (regularly, from time to time, never)</p> <p>a) public</p> <p>b) private</p> <p>c) public/private</p> <p>d) non-profit</p> <p>e) others</p>	<p>How often do you collaborate with the following organisations in your day-to-day business? (regularly, from time to time, never)</p> <p>a) public</p> <p>b) private</p> <p>c) public/private</p> <p>d) non-profit</p> <p>e) others</p>
	<p>Many hazards have cross-border impacts. Therefore, it is important to have networks across national borders to ensure that risk-related messages reach members of the public at risk.</p>	<p>Many hazards have cross-border impacts. Therefore, it is important to have networks across national borders to ensure that risk-related messages reach members of the public at risk.</p>	<p>Many hazards have cross-border impacts. Therefore, it is important to have networks across national borders to ensure that risk-related messages reach members of the public at risk.</p>	<p>Many hazards have cross-border impacts. Therefore, it is important to have networks across national borders to ensure that risk-related messages reach members of the public at risk.</p>
14	<p>How regularly are you in contact with organisations from neighbouring countries?</p> <p>a) Regularly</p> <p>b) From time to time</p> <p>c) Never (proceed with question 17)</p>	<p>How regularly are you in contact with organisations from neighbouring countries?</p> <p>a) Regularly</p> <p>b) From time to time</p> <p>c) Never (proceed with question 17)</p>	<p>How regularly are you in contact with organisations from neighbouring countries?</p> <p>a) Regularly</p> <p>b) From time to time</p> <p>c) Never (proceed with question 17)</p>	<p>How regularly are you in contact with organisations from neighbouring countries?</p> <p>a) Regularly</p> <p>b) From time to time</p> <p>c) Never (proceed with question 17)</p>

15	<p>Do you have communication plans with organisations from your neighbouring countries that might be affected by a terrorist attack?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you have communication plans with organisations from your neighbouring countries that might be affected by a flood event?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you have communication plans with organisations from your neighbouring countries that might likewise be affected by a large epidemic event?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you have communication plans with organisations from your neighbouring countries that might likewise be affected by a large earthquake event?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
16	<p>Do you face language barriers in communicating with your neighbouring countries?</p> <p>a) No, we don't face language barriers b) Yes, we have taken actions to minimize barriers c) Yes, we face language barriers, but we have not taken actions yet. d) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you face language barriers in communicating with your neighbouring countries?</p> <p>a) No, we don't face language barriers b) Yes, we have taken actions to minimize barriers c) Yes, we face language barriers, but we have not taken actions yet. d) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you face language barriers in communicating with your neighbouring countries?</p> <p>a) No, we don't face language barriers b) Yes, we have taken actions to minimize barriers c) Yes, we face language barriers, but we have not taken actions yet. d) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you face language barriers in communicating with your target audience?</p> <p>a) No, we don't face language barriers b) Yes, we have taken actions to minimize barriers c) Yes, we face language barriers, but we have not taken actions yet. d) I don't know</p>
	<p>Now we would like to learn more about your risk communication activities for terrorism. We are particularly interested in your organisation's previous experience with risk communication. We have identified four potential communication aims. By</p>	<p>Now we would like to learn more about your flood risk communication activities for flood events. We are particularly interested in your organisation's previous experience with risk communication. We have identified four potential communication aims. By answering questions related to these aims, TACTIC is able to provide you with</p>	<p>Now we would like to learn more about your flood risk communication activities for epidemics. We are particularly interested in your organisation's previous experience with risk communication. We have identified four potential communication aims. By</p>	<p>Now we would like to learn more about your earthquake risk communication activities for earthquake events. We are particularly interested in your organisation's previous experience with risk communication. We have identified four potential</p>

	answering questions related to these aims, TACTIC is able to provide you with feedback in regards to your organisation's strengths and weaknesses that exist in regards to meeting your aims. You will also be provided with suggestions for improvement upon completion of the self-assessment survey.	feedback in regards to your organisation's strengths and weaknesses that exist in regards to meeting your aims. You will also be provided with suggestions for improvement upon completion of the self-assessment survey.	answering questions related to these aims, TACTIC is able to provide you with feedback in regards to your organisation's strengths and weaknesses that exist in regards to meeting your aims. You will also be provided with suggestions for improvement upon completion of the self-assessment survey.	communication aims. By answering questions related to these aims, TACTIC is able to provide you with feedback in regards to your organisation's strengths and weaknesses that exist in regards to meeting your aims. You will also be provided with suggestions for improvement upon completion of the self-assessment survey.
17	<p>How important is risk communication in your organisation in comparison to other activities that your organisation is responsible for?</p> <p>a) Important b) Unimportant c) I don't know</p>	<p>How important is risk communication in your organisation in comparison to other activities that your organisation is responsible for?</p> <p>a) Important b) Unimportant c) I don't know</p>	<p>How important is risk communication in your organisation in comparison to other activities that your organisation is responsible for?</p> <p>a) Important b) Unimportant c) I don't know</p>	<p>How important is risk communication in your organisation in comparison to other activities that your organisation is responsible for?</p> <p>a) Important b) Unimportant c) I don't know</p>
18	<p>In your opinion, how well are you and your organisation equipped with resources to communicate risk in your community/city/region?</p> <p>Well equipped Poorly equipped I don't know</p> <p>a. Finances (money, sources of funding, etc.)</p>	<p>In your opinion, how well are you and your organisation equipped with resources to communicate risk in your community/city/region?</p> <p>Well equipped Poorly equipped I don't know</p> <p>a. Finances (money, sources of funding, etc.) b. Staff (personnel)</p>	<p>In your opinion, how well are you and your organisation equipped with resources to communicate risk in your community/city/region?</p> <p>Well equipped Poorly equipped I don't know</p> <p>a. Finances (money, sources of funding, etc.)</p>	<p>In your opinion, how well are you and your organisation equipped with resources to communicate risk in your community/city/region?</p> <p>Well equipped Poorly equipped I don't know</p> <p>a. Finances (money, sources of funding, etc.)</p>

	<p>b. Staff (personnel)</p> <p>c. Knowledge (knowledge about risk and risk reduction, risk communication knowledge, etc.)</p> <p>d. Skills (e.g., designing information material, communicating prevention measures)</p> <p>e. Motivation (desire to actively reduce the risk of terrorism in your community/ increase preparedness for terrorism)</p>	<p>c. Knowledge (knowledge about risk and risk reduction, risk communication knowledge, etc.)</p> <p>d. Skills (e.g., designing information material, communicating prevention measures)</p> <p>e. Motivation (desire to actively reduce the risk of flooding in your community/ increase preparedness for flooding)</p>	<p>b. Staff (personnel)</p> <p>c. Knowledge (knowledge about risk and risk reduction, risk communication knowledge, etc.)</p> <p>d. Skills (e.g., designing information material, demonstration of health protection measures)</p> <p>e. Motivation (desire to actively promote health in your community)</p> <p>f. Built infrastructure (in good condition meeting safety and regulatory standards)</p>	<p>b. Staff (personnel)</p> <p>c. Knowledge (knowledge about risk and risk reduction, risk communication knowledge, etc.)</p> <p>d. Skills (e.g., designing information material, communicating earthquake protection measures)</p> <p>e. Motivation (desire to actively increase earthquake preparedness in your community)</p>
19	<p>Does your organisation have a risk communication strategy covering communicating the risk of terrorism?</p> <p>a) Yes, and I think it is excellent in practice</p> <p>b) Yes, but it needs improvement</p> <p>c) No</p> <p>d) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a risk communication strategy covering communicating the risk of flooding?</p> <p>a) Yes, and I think it is excellent in practice</p> <p>b) Yes, but it needs improvement</p> <p>c) No</p> <p>d) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a risk communication strategy?</p> <p>a) Yes, and I think it is excellent in practice</p> <p>b) Yes, but it needs improvement</p> <p>c) No</p> <p>d) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a risk communication strategy covering communicating earthquake risk?</p> <p>a) Yes, and I think it is excellent in practice</p> <p>b) Yes, but it needs improvement</p> <p>c) No</p> <p>d) I don't know</p>
20	<p>Do you believe that the general public trusts the information that your organisation is communicating?</p>	<p>Do you believe that the general public trusts the information that your organisation is communicating?</p> <p>a) Yes</p>	<p>Do you believe that the general public trusts the information that your organisation is communicating?</p>	<p>Do you believe that the general public trusts the information that your organisation is communicating?</p>

	a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	b) No c) I don't know	a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	a) Yes b) No c) I don't know
21	<p>Please specify which of the following aims are relevant for your organisation's risk communication activities related specifically to the risk of terrorism. Please tick all that apply.</p> <p><i>Although, in practice, these four aims of risk communication overlap, they are still conceptually different. Therefore, based on the research evidence and in order to simplify the task ahead, we will only focus on these four aims.</i></p> <p>a) Raising risk awareness (i.e. informing people about risks well before an event occurs)</p> <p>b) Strengthening capacities to act (informing people about what to do in case of an emergency, knowing how to prevent terrorism, etc. before an event)</p> <p>c) Warning in case of emergency (what is known about an impending attack, how should</p>	<p>Please specify which of the following aims are relevant for your organisation's risk communication activities. Please tick all that apply.</p> <p><i>Although, in practice, these four aims of risk communication overlap, they are still conceptually different. Therefore, based on the research evidence and in order to simplify the task ahead, we will only focus on these four aims.</i></p> <p>a) Raising risk awareness (i.e. informing people about risks well before an event occurs)</p> <p>b) Strengthening capacities to act (informing people about what to do in case of an emergency, building houses with earthquake protection and mitigation measures etc. before an event)</p> <p>c) Warning in case of emergency (when and where the epidemic threat is identified, what needs to be done by the population etc.)</p> <p>d) Resolving conflicts and building trust (e.g. disputes about appropriate measures, tensions between different</p>	<p>Please specify which of the following aims are relevant for your organisation's risk communication activities. Please tick all that apply.</p> <p><i>Although, in practice, these four aims of risk communication overlap, they are still conceptually different. Therefore, based on the research evidence and in order to simplify the task ahead, we will only focus on these four aims.</i></p> <p>a) Raising risk awareness (i.e. informing people about risks well before an event occurs)</p> <p>b) Strengthening capacities to act (informing people about what to do in case of an emergency, building houses with earthquake protection and mitigation measures etc. before an event)</p> <p>c) Warning in case of emergency (when and where the epidemic threat is identified, what needs to be done by the population etc.)</p>	<p>Please specify which of the following aims are relevant for your organisation's risk communication activities. Please tick all that apply.</p> <p><i>Although, in practice, these four aims of risk communication overlap, they are still conceptually different. Therefore, based on the research evidence and in order to simplify the task ahead, we will only focus on these four aims.</i></p> <p>a) Raising risk awareness (i.e. informing people about risks well before an event occurs)</p> <p>b) Strengthening capacities to act (informing people about what to do in case of an emergency, building houses with earthquake protection and mitigation measures etc. before an event)</p> <p>d) Resolving conflicts and building trust (e.g. disputes about appropriate measures, tensions between different groups of the community, etc.)</p>

	the population respond, etc.) d) Resolving conflicts and building trust (e.g. disputes about appropriate measures, tensions between different groups of the community, etc.)	groups of the community, etc.)	d) Resolving conflicts and building trust (e.g. disputes about appropriate measures, tensions between different groups of the community, etc.)	
	<u>Aim: Raising risk awareness</u> Raising risk awareness involves informing the public about the different types of terrorist threat (e.g., bombings, firearms attack, chemical attack, cyber-terrorism) well before such an event occurs.	<u>Aim: Raising risk awareness</u> Raising risk awareness involves informing the public about the type, the expected intensity, probability and the anticipated consequences of the hazard event well before such an event occurs.	<u>Aim: Raising risk awareness</u> Raising risk awareness involves informing the public about the type, the expected intensity, probability and the anticipated consequences of the hazard event well before such an event occurs.	<u>Aim: Raising risk awareness</u> Raising hazard awareness involves informing the public about the type, the expected intensity, probability and the anticipated consequences of the event well before such an event occurs.
22	Do you provide information about the risk of terrorism to your community/city/region (e.g. the likelihood of certain types of terrorism occurring in the community/city/region perhaps through examples that have taken place in the past)? a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know	Do you provide information about the risk of flooding to your community/city/region (e.g. Information about the probability of flooding occurring in the future in the community/city/region and what the consequences might be/have been in the past)? a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know	Do you provide information about epidemic risks to your community/city/region (e.g. information about the types of epidemics that could occur at what time of year and how they spread)? a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know	Do you provide information about earthquake risks to your community/city/region (information about the probability of earthquakes occurring in the community (city/region and what the consequences might be/have been in the past)? a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know

23	<p>In order to raise risk awareness of terrorism, do you use?:</p> <p>a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>b) Simple language (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/ I don't know)</p>	<p>In order to raise risk awareness of floods, do you use....?:</p> <p>a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>b) Simple language (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/ I don't know)</p>	<p>In order to raise risk awareness of epidemics, do you use....?:</p> <p>a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>b) Simple language (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/ I don't know)</p>	<p>In order to raise risk awareness of earthquakes, do you use....?:</p> <p>a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>b) Simple language (yes/no/ I don't know)</p> <p>c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/ I don't know)</p>
24	<p>Which methods do you use for raising awareness of the risk of terrorism? (multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Mass media</p> <p>a) Website</p> <p>b) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes)</p>	<p>Which methods do you use for raising awareness of the risk of floods? (multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Mass media</p> <p>a) Website</p> <p>b) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes)</p> <p>c) Television</p>	<p>Which methods do you use for raising awareness of epidemic risk? (multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Mass media</p> <p>a) Website</p> <p>b) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes)</p> <p>c) Television</p>	<p>Which methods do you use for raising awareness of the risk of earthquake? (multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Mass media</p> <p>a) Website</p> <p>b) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes)</p>

	<p>c) Television Information materials d) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. e) Movies, Podcasts Technology-assisted communication f) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System Social media g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other Face-to-face communication j) Public meetings/hearings k) Public workshops l) Round table discussion m) Theatre plays Stakeholder participation n) Role-playing o) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) Visualisation of risk p) Photos q) Posters and displays r) Direct advertising s) Videos t) Others</p>	<p>Information materials d) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. e) Movies, Podcasts Technology-assisted communication f) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System Social media g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other Face-to-face communication j) Public meetings/hearings k) Public workshops l) Round table discussion m) Theatre plays Stakeholder participation n) Role-playing o) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) Visualisation of risk p) Photos q) Posters and displays r) Direct advertising s) Videos t) Others</p>	<p>Information materials d) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. e) Movies, Podcasts Technology-assisted communication f) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System Social media g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other Face-to-face communication j) Public meetings/hearings k) Public workshops l) Round table discussion m) Theatre plays Stakeholder participation n) Role-playing o) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) Visualisation of risk p) Photos q) Posters and displays r) Direct advertising s) Videos t) Others</p>	<p>c) Television Information materials d) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. e) Movies, Podcasts Technology-assisted communication f) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System Social media g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other Face-to-face communication j) Public meetings/hearings k) Public workshops l) Round table discussion m) Theatre plays Stakeholder participation n) Role-playing o) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) Visualisation of risk p) Photos q) Posters and displays r) Direct advertising s) Videos t) Others</p>
25	Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people	Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special	Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people	Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people

	<p>who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>
26	<p>Communication habits and information needs to differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs to differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs to differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs to differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>
27	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach the aim of raising risk awareness? One example could be: "Citizens should be aware of the risk of terrorist attacks."</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach the aim of raising risk awareness? One example could be: "Citizens are responsible for reducing flood risk at their property."</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach the aim of raising risk awareness? One example could be: "Citizens are responsible for informing themselves about the risk of an epidemic outbreak."</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach the aim of raising risk awareness? One example could be: "Citizens are responsible for reducing earthquake risk at their property."</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>

28	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of raising awareness?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of raising risk awareness?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of raising risk awareness?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of raising risk awareness?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
29	<p>If yes: Are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices designed to raise awareness of the risk of terrorism?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes: Are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices designed to raise awareness of the risk of flooding?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes: Are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices designed to raise awareness of the risk of epidemics?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes: Are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices designed to raise awareness of the risk of earthquakes?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
	<p><u>Aim: Strengthening capacities to act</u> Strengthening capacities to act involves, for instance, providing information on how communities can take action well in advance of</p>	<p><u>Aim: Strengthening capacities to act</u> Strengthening capacities to act involves, for instance, providing information on how communities can take action well in advance of a flood event to enhance their response or mitigate the</p>	<p><u>Aim: Strengthening capacities to act</u> Strengthening capacities to act involves, for instance, providing information on how communities can take action well in advance of</p>	<p><u>Aim: Strengthening capacities to act</u> Strengthening capacities to act involves, for instance, providing information on how communities can take action well in advance of</p>

	a terrorist attack to enhance their response.	consequences.	a an epidemic event to enhance their response or mitigate the consequences.	a earthquake event to enhance their response or mitigate the consequences.
30	<p>Do you provide information about how residents in your community/city/region can prepare themselves for a terrorist attack?</p> <p>a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you provide information about how residents in your community/city/region can prepare themselves for a flood event?</p> <p>a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you provide information about how residents of your community/city/region can prepare themselves for epidemics?</p> <p>a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you provide information about how residents of your community/city/region can prepare themselves for earthquakes?</p> <p>a) Yes, regularly b) Yes, from time to time c) No d) I don't know</p>
31	<p>In order to raise the capacity to act, how regularly does your organisation inform your community/city/region about the following issues?</p> <p>Regularly From time to time Never I don't know</p> <p>a) Preventing terrorism (e.g., vigilance and reporting suspicious activities or packages, security measures to protect electronic items from cyber-terrorism) b) Avoiding certain activities</p>	<p>In order to raise the capacity to act, how regularly does your organisation inform your community/city/region about the following issues?</p> <p>Regularly From time to time Never I don't know</p> <p>a) How to read and understand flood hazard and risk maps b) Rain water management on individual property c) How to insure buildings against damage from natural disasters d) Preparation of individual flood emergency / evacuation plan for</p>	<p>In order to raise the capacity to act, how regularly does your organisation inform your community/city/region about the following issues?</p> <p>Regularly From time to time Never I don't know</p> <p>a) Preparing your home for an epidemic b) How to interpret epidemic risk communications c) Infectious disease control measures and policies d) Information about keeping</p>	<p>In order to raise the capacity to act, how regularly does your organisation inform your community/city/region about the following issues?</p> <p>Regularly From time to time Never I don't know</p> <p>a) Earthquake-safe construction or about earthquake protection in buildings b) How to read and understand earthquake hazard and risk maps c) Safe evacuation and</p>

	<p>to reduce the risk of terrorism (e.g., avoiding travelling to certain countries)</p> <p>c) Preparation of an individual/family emergency plan including how to respond to a terrorist attack</p> <p>d) Preparation of an emergency kit including medical supplies and copies of important documents</p> <p>e) Information about local emergency plans covering terrorism</p>	<p>family, small firm or farm</p> <p>e) Emergency kit: Appropriate behaviour in case of emergency (e.g. store important documents, medicine, phone numbers ready, evacuation procedures)</p> <p>f) Financial aid for reconstruction after floods?</p> <p>g) Elevation of furnace, water heater and electrical panel</p> <p>h) Installation of „check valves“</p> <p>i) Construction of barriers (concrete walls / earth levees) to stop floodwater from entering the building</p> <p>j) Preparation of mobile barriers on basement windows and doors</p> <p>k) Appropriate floor material on the ground floor</p> <p>l) Sealed walls in the basement with waterproofing compounds</p>	<p>individuals/families/ animals healthy during an epidemic</p> <p>e) Preparation of epidemic emergency plans for families, small business or farms</p> <p>f) Emergency kits: Appropriate behaviour in case of emergency (e.g. store important documents, emergency supplies, medicines, phone numbers ready, evacuation procedures)</p> <p>g) Insurance against epidemic-related damages</p> <p>h) Financial aid for recovery after epidemics</p>	<p>emergency escape routes</p> <p>d) Information about earthquake resistance/building codes</p> <p>e) Non-structural risk mitigation on individual property (e.g. good practise in stabilizing and arranging furniture)</p> <p>f) How to insure buildings against damage from natural disasters</p> <p>g) Preparation of individual earthquake emergency / evacuation plan for family, small firm or farm</p> <p>h) Preparation of an earthquake family reunion plan</p> <p>i) Information about what to put into an earthquake emergency kit (e.g. store important documents, medicine, phone numbers, evacuation procedures)</p> <p>j) Appropriate behaviour for emergency (e.g. store important documents, medicine, phone numbers ready, evacuation procedures)</p> <p>k) Concrete example of what to do in the case of an earthquake event (e.g. “drop, cover and hold on”)</p>
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32	<p>In order to strengthening the capacities of residents to act, do you use ...? (multiple answers possible):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/I don't know) b) Simple language (yes/no/I don't know)) c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/I don't know) 	<p>In order to strengthening the capacities of residents to act, do you use...? (multiple answers possible):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/I don't know)) b) Simple language (yes/no/I don't know)) c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/I don't know) 	<p>In order to strengthening the capacities of residents to act, do you use...? (multiple answers possible):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/I don't know)) b) Simple language (yes/no/I don't know)) c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/I don't know)) 	<p>In order to strengthening the capacities of residents to act, do you use...? (multiple answers possible):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) simple, graphical, and factual materials (yes/no/I don't know)) b) Simple language (yes/no/I don't know) c) Vivid examples and stories that communicate on a personal level (yes/no/I don't know))
33		<p>When you communicate with the general public, does your organisation emphasise the potential benefits of taking these actions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No c) I don't know 	<p>When you communicate with the general public, does your organisation emphasise the potential benefits of taking these actions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No c) I don't know 	<p>When you communicate with the general public, does your organisation emphasise the potential benefits of taking these actions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No c) I don't know

34	<p>Do you communicate your roles and responsibility as an organisation for managing the risk of terrorism to the general public?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know d) No – we are legally not allowed to share this information with the public</p>	<p>Do you communicate your roles and responsibility as an organisation for managing the risk of flooding to the general public?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you communicate your roles and responsibility as an organisation for managing the risk of epidemics to the general public?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you communicate your roles and responsibility as an organisation for managing the risk of earthquakes to the general public?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
35	<p>Do you communicate the responsibilities and rights of the general public with regards to terrorism?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you communicate the responsibilities and rights of the general public with regards to flooding?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you communicate the responsibilities and rights of the general public with regards to epidemics?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you communicate the responsibilities and rights of the general public with regards to earthquakes?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
36	<p>Do you actively involve members of the general public in discussions about how to prepare for terrorism?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) No, we legally are not allowed to d) I don't know e)</p>	<p>Do you actively involve members of the general public in discussions about how to prepare for floods?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you actively involve members of the general public in discussions about how to prepare for epidemics?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you actively involve members of the general public in discussions about how to prepare for earthquakes?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>

<p>37</p>	<p>When you communicate with the public in order to strengthen capacities with regard to terrorism, which methods do you use? (Multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Public meetings/hearings d) Public workshops e) IRound table discussion f) Theatre plays <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g) SMS h) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System <p>Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Twitter, j) Facebook k) Other <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Website m) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) n) Television/Radio o) Information materials p) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. q) Movies, Podcasts 	<p>When you communicate with the public in order to strengthen capacities with regard to the risk of flooding, which methods do you use? (Multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Public meetings/hearings d) Public workshops e) Round table discussion f) Theatre plays <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g) SMS h) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System <p>Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Twitter, j) Facebook k) Other <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Website m) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) o) n) Television/Radio/Information materials p) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. q) Movies, Podcasts 	<p>When you communicate with the public in order to strengthen capacities with regard to epidemic risks, which methods do you use? (Multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) j) Public meetings/hearings d) k) Public workshops e) l) Round table discussion f) m) Theatre plays <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g) SMS h) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System <p>Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Twitter j) Facebook k) Other <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Website m) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) n) Television/Radio 	<p>When you communicate with the public in order to strengthen capacities with regard to the risk of an earthquake event, which methods do you use? (Multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Public meetings/hearings d) Public workshops e) Round table discussion f) Theatre plays <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g) SMS h) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System <p>Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Twitter j) Facebook k) Other <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Website m) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) n) Television/Radio o) Information materials p) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. q) Movies, Podcasts
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	<p>Visualisation of risk</p> <p>r) Photos</p> <p>s) Posters and displays</p> <p>t) Direct advertising</p> <p>u) Videos</p> <p>v) Others</p>	<p>Visualisation of risk</p> <p>r) Photos</p> <p>s) Posters and displays</p> <p>t) Direct advertising</p> <p>u) Videos</p> <p>v) Others</p>	<p>o) Information materials</p> <p>p) Brochures, Leaflets, etc.</p> <p>q) Movies, Podcasts</p> <p>Visualisation of risk</p> <p>r) Photos</p> <p>s) Posters and displays</p> <p>t) Direct advertising</p> <p>u) Videos</p> <p>v) Others</p>	<p>Visualisation of risk</p> <p>r) Photos</p> <p>s) Posters and displays</p> <p>t) Direct advertising</p> <p>u) Videos</p> <p>v) Others)</p>
38	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>
39	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.). Do you take such differences into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.). Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.). Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.). Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>
40	<p>Do you take psychological factors</p>	<p>Do you take psychological factors (e.g.</p>	<p>Do you take psychological factors</p>	<p>Do you take psychological factors</p>

	(e.g. risk perceptions and motivations) into account when providing information about preparedness actions? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	risk perceptions and motivations) into account when providing information about preparedness actions? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	(e.g. risk perceptions and motivations) into account when providing information about preparedness actions? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	(e.g. risk perceptions and motivations) into account when providing information about preparedness actions? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know
41	Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "Create an emergency plan for responding to a terrorist attack!/to avoid a cyber-attack, ensure that your firewalls are updated regularly." a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "Your actions can reduce flood-related damage." a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "Washing your hands regularly can reduce your chances of becoming infected with influenza." a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "In the event of an earthquake, drop, cover and hold on." a) Yes b) No c) I don't know
42	Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of strengthening the public's capacity to respond to a terrorist attack? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of strengthening the public's capacity to respond to a flood event? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of strengthening the public's capacity to respond to an epidemic? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know	Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of strengthening the public's capacity to respond to an earthquake? a) Yes b) No c) I don't know

43	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices related to terrorism?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices related to floods?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices related to epidemics?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices related to earthquakes?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
	<p><u>Aim: Warning in case of emergency</u> Timely and clear warning in case of a terrorist attack can reduce its impact and might even save lives.</p>	<p><u>Aim: Warning in case of emergency</u> Timely and clear informing in case of emergency can reduce flood-related damage and might even save lives in case of an emergency.</p>	<p><u>Aim: Warning in case of emergency</u> Timely and clear warning in case of emergency can slow the spread of an epidemic and might even save lives in case of an emergency.</p>	
44	<p>Did you warn people in the past about a likely terrorist attack?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (continue with 46) c) I don't know</p>	<p>Did you warn people about an epidemic event in the past?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (continue with 46) c) I don't know</p>	<p>Did you warn people about an epidemic event in the past?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (continue with 46) c) I don't know</p>	
45	<p>Please state whether you agree with the following statements:</p> <p>Yes No I Don't know</p>	<p>Please state whether you agree with the following statements:</p> <p>Yes No I don't know</p>	<p>Please state whether you agree with the following statements:</p> <p>Yes No I don't know</p>	

	<p>a) The warning was very precise (e.g. time and location)</p> <p>b) The warning provided no contradictory information</p> <p>c) The warning was very timely</p> <p>d) People have received too many false warnings in the past and therefore did not trust our last warning</p> <p>e) We have used multiple channels to reach out to the general public in the event of an emergency</p> <p>f) We did not reach our audience since our communication channels were insufficient</p> <p>g) others</p>	<p>a). The warning was very precise (e.g. time and location)</p> <p>b) The warning provided no contradictory information</p> <p>c) The warning was very timely</p> <p>d) People have received too many false warnings in the past and therefore did not trust our last warning</p> <p>e) We have used multiple channels to reach out to the general public in the event of an emergency</p> <p>f) We did not reach our audience since our communication channels were insufficient</p> <p>g) others</p>	<p>a) The warning was very precise (e.g. time and location)</p> <p>b) The warning provided no contradictory information</p> <p>c) The warning was very timely</p> <p>d) People have received too many false warnings in the past and therefore did not trust our last warning</p> <p>e) We have used multiple channels to reach out to the general public in the event of an emergency</p> <p>f) We did not reach our audience since our communication channels were insufficient</p> <p>g) others</p>	
46	<p>Which methods will you use for warning the population about a likely terrorist attack in the future?</p> <p>[multiple answers possible]</p> <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <p>a) SMS</p> <p>b) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System</p> <p>c) Sirens</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>d) Twitter</p>	<p>Which methods will you use for warning the population about a likely flood event in the future?</p> <p>[multiple answers possible]</p> <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <p>a) SMS</p> <p>b) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System</p> <p>c) Sirens</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>d) Twitter</p> <p>e) Facebook</p> <p>f) Other</p>	<p>Which methods will you use for warning the population about a likely epidemic in the future?</p> <p>[multiple answers possible]</p> <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <p>a) SMS</p> <p>b) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System</p> <p>c) Sirens</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>d) Twitter</p>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e) Facebook f) Other <p>Visualisation of risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g) Photos h) Posters and displays i) Direct advertising j) Videos <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> k) Website l) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) m) Television or Radio <p>Information materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> n) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. o) Movies, Podcasts <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> p) Public meetings/hearings q) Public workshops r) Round table discussion <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s) Role-playing t) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) u) Others 	<p>Visualisation of risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g) Photos h) Posters and displays i) Direct advertising j) Videos <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> k) Website l) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) m) Television or Radio <p>Information materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> n) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. o) Movies, Podcasts <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> p) Public meetings/hearings q) Public workshops r) Round table discussion <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s) Role-playing t) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) u) Others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e) Facebook f) Other <p>Visualisation of risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g) Photos h) Posters and displays i) Direct advertising j) Videos <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> k) Website l) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) m) Television or Radio <p>Information materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> n) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. o) Movies, Podcasts <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> p) Public meetings/hearings q) Public workshops r) Round table discussion <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s) Role-playing t) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise) u) Others 	
47	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Yes b. No 	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Yes b. No c. I don't know 	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Yes b. No 	

	c. I don't know		c. I don't know	
48	<p>Do you take into account the preferred methods of communication of different groups in your community/city/region when warning the general public (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, SMS, TV, etc.)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>Do you take into account the preferred methods of communication of different groups in your community/city/region when warning the general public (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, SMS, TV, etc.)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>Do you take into account the preferred methods of communication of different groups in your community/city/region when warning the general public (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, SMS, TV, etc.)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	
49	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "In the event of a terrorist attack, run and hide!"</p> <p>a. a) Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "Your actions can reduce flood-related damage."</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "Washing your hands regularly can reduce your chances of becoming infected with influenza."</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	
50	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of warning?</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of</p>	

	<p>warning?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>warning?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	
51	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No d. Don I don't know</p>	
	<p><u>Aim: Resolving conflicts and building trust</u> Resolving problems and conflicts related to risk communication and consequently rebuilding trust before and after events are key elements of a functioning and effective communication strategy</p>	<p><u>Aim: Resolving conflicts and building trust</u> Resolving problems and conflicts related to risk communication and consequently rebuilding trust before and after events are key elements of a functioning and effective communication strategy</p>	<p><u>Aim: Resolving conflicts and building trust</u> Resolving problems and conflicts related to risk communication and consequently rebuilding trust before and after events are key elements of a functioning and effective communication strategy</p>	<p><u>Aim: Resolving conflicts and building trust</u> Resolving problems and conflicts related to risk communication and consequently rebuilding trust before and after events are key elements of a functioning and effective communication strategy</p>
52	<p>Are you aware of any conflicts concerning potential terrorist threats in your community/city/region?</p> <p>a) Yes</p>	<p>Are you aware of any conflicts between your organisation and the general public concerning the management of potential flood events in your community/city/region?</p>	<p>Are you aware of any conflicts between your organisation and the general public concerning the management of epidemic risk in your community/city/region?</p>	<p>Are you aware of any conflicts between your organisation and the general public concerning the management of earthquake risk in your community/city/region?</p>

	<p>b) No (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p> <p>c) I don't know (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p>	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p> <p>c) I don't know (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p>	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p> <p>c) I don't know (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p>	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p> <p>c) I don't know (continue with first question from the next aim chosen or to the end of the assessment)</p>
53	<p>Have you taken efforts to understand what the actual source of the conflict is (e.g. diverging interests and world-views)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Have you taken efforts to understand what the actual source of the conflict is (e.g. diverging interests, exclusion of stakeholder from the decision-making process etc.)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Have you taken efforts to understand opposing viewpoints in the conflict (e.g. diverging interests, exclusion of stakeholder from the decision-making process etc.)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Have you taken efforts to understand what the actual problem of the conflict is (e.g. diverging interests, exclusion of stakeholder from the decision-making process etc.)?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>
54	<p>In order to solve the conflict, did you involve members of the general public from the beginning of the decision-making process?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>In order to solve the conflict, did you involve members of the general public from the beginning of the decision-making process?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>In order to solve the conflict, did you involve members of the general public from the beginning of the decision-making process?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>In order to solve the conflict, did you involve members of the general public from the beginning of the decision-making process?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>

55	<p>In order to solve a conflict, the process needs a clear objective that is agreed upon by all relevant stakeholders from the outset. Have you agreed on the overall objective of the conflict solving process?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>In order to solve a conflict, the process needs a clear objective that is agreed upon by all relevant stakeholders from the outset. Have you agreed on the overall objective of the conflict solving process?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>In order to solve a conflict, the process needs a clear objective that is agreed upon by all relevant stakeholders from the outset. Have you agreed on the overall objective of the conflict solving process?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>In order to solve a conflict, the process needs a clear objective that is agreed upon by all relevant stakeholders from the outset. Have you agreed on the overall objective of the conflict solving process?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
56	<p>In many cases it is vital for the process that it is lead, moderated and facilitated by an independent and experienced external moderator. Have you involved an external moderator?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>In many cases it is vital for the process that it is lead, moderated and facilitated by an independent and experienced external moderator. Have you involved an external moderator?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>In many cases it is vital for the process that it is lead, moderated and facilitated by an independent and experienced external moderator. Have you involved an external moderator?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>In many cases it is vital for the process that it is lead, moderated and facilitated by an independent and experienced external moderator. Have you involved an external moderator?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
57	<p>Agreement on specific actions is essential for the sustainability of the conflict-solution. Have you agreed on specific follow-up steps that different actors need to take?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No</p>	<p>Agreement on specific actions is essential for the sustainability of the conflict-solution. Have you agreed on specific follow-up steps that different actors need to take?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No</p>	<p>Agreement on specific actions is essential for the sustainability of the conflict-solution. Have you agreed on specific follow-up steps that different actors need to take?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No</p>	<p>Agreement on specific actions is essential for the sustainability of the conflict-solution. Have you agreed on specific follow-up steps that different actors need to take?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No</p>

	c) I don't know			
58	<p>Are you in contact with the media in order to ensure that messages are clear and concise in order to avoid conflict being instigated by the media (e.g. mass media/press)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you in contact with the media in order to ensure that messages are clear and concise in order to avoid conflict being instigated by the media (e.g. mass media/press)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you in contact with the media in order to ensure that messages are clear and concise in order to avoid conflict being instigated by the media (e.g. mass media/press)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you in contact with the media in order to ensure that messages are clear and concise in order to avoid conflict being instigated by the media (e.g. mass media/press)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>

<p>59</p>	<p>Which method do you use for addressing conflicts concerning the risk of terrorism or the management of terrorism?</p> <p>(multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <p>a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise)</p> <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <p>c) Public meetings/hearings d) Public workshops e) Round table discussion f) Theatre plays</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other</p> <p>Information materials</p> <p>j) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. k) Movies, Podcasts</p>	<p>Which method do you use for addressing conflicts concerning the risk of flooding or flood risk management? (multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <p>a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise)</p> <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <p>c) Public meetings/hearings d) Public workshops e) Round table discussion f) Theatre plays</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other</p> <p>Information materials</p> <p>j) Brochures, Leaflets, etc.</p>	<p>Which method do you use for resolving and preventing conflicts concerning epidemic risk or epidemic risk management? (multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <p>a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise)</p> <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <p>c) Public meetings/hearings d) Public workshops e) Round table discussion f) Theatre plays</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other</p> <p>Information materials</p> <p>j) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. k) Movies, Podcasts</p>	<p>Which method do you use for resolving and preventing conflicts concerning earthquake risk or earthquake risk management? (multiple answers possible)</p> <p>Stakeholder participation</p> <p>a) Role-playing b) Simulations (e.g. emergency exercise)</p> <p>Face-to-face communication</p> <p>c) Public meetings/hearings d) Public workshops e) Round table discussion f) Theatre plays</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>g) Twitter h) Facebook i) Other</p> <p>Information materials</p> <p>j) Brochures, Leaflets, etc. k) Movies, Podcasts</p>
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	<p>Visualisation of risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Photos m) Posters and displays n) Direct advertising o) Videos <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> p) Website q) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) r) Television or Radio <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s) SMS t) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System u) Others 	<p>k) Movies, Podcasts</p> <p>Visualisation of risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Photos m) Posters and displays n) Direct advertising o) Videos <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> p) Website q) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) r) Television or Radio <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s) SMS t) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System u) Others 	<p>Visualisation of risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Photos m) Posters and displays n) Direct advertising o) Videos <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> p) Website q) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) r) Television or Radio <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s) SMS t) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System u)) Others 	<p>Visualisation of risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> l) Photos m) Posters and displays n) Direct advertising o) Videos <p>Mass media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> p) Website q) Publication in local/regional newspapers (incl. official gazettes) r) Television or Radio <p>Technology-assisted communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s) SMS t) Automatic Voice/Phone Notification System u)) Others
60	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p>	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p>	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p>	<p>Do you reach out to different groups in your community/city/region (people who use other languages, special communication needs, etc.)?</p>

	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>
61	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such differences into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Communication habits and information needs differ between groups (e.g. some people may prefer to receive information via email, newspaper, TV, etc.)? Do you take such difference into account in your risk communication?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>

<p>62</p>	<p>Do you take psychological factors (e.g. risk perceptions and motivations) into account when resolving conflicts and building trust?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you take psychological factors (e.g. risk perceptions and motivations) into account when resolving conflicts and building trust?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you take psychological factors (e.g. risk perceptions and motivations) into account when resolving conflicts and building trust?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Do you take psychological factors (e.g. risk perceptions and motivations) into account when providing resolving conflicts and building trust?</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>
<p>63</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "preparedness can be effectively achieved when we all work together"</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "preparedness can be effectively achieved when we all work together"</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "preparedness can be effectively achieved when we all work together"</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>	<p>Does your organisation have a key message which is communicated to reach this aim? This could for example be something like "preparedness can be effectively achieved when we all work together"</p> <p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p> <p>c) I don't know</p>

64	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of joint problem solving and resolving conflict related to the risk of terrorism?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of joint problem solving and resolving conflict related to the risk of flooding?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to this aim?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>Are you actively collecting feedback on your communication practices related to the aim of joint problem-solving and resolving conflict related to the risk earthquake?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>
65	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>	<p>If yes, are you using the feedback to improve your communication practices?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No c) I don't know</p>

	<p>Congratulations! You have completed the TACTIC's Self-Assessment for organisations.</p> <p>Click here to receive feedback on you results (add link)</p>	<p>Congratulations! You have completed the TACTIC's Self-Assessment for organisations.</p> <p>Click here to receive feedback on you results (add link)</p>	<p>Congratulations! You have completed the TACTIC's Self-Assessment for organisations.</p> <p>Click here to receive feedback on you results (add link)</p>	<p>Congratulations! You have completed the TACTIC's Self-Assessment for organisations.</p> <p>Click here to receive feedback on you results (add link)</p>
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7.2. The GPSA

In comparison to the OSA, only a few adjustments were made to the GPSA.

Terrorism	Floods	Epidemics	Earthquakes
<p>Welcome to the Preparedness-Check for the general public on “Terrorism”!</p> <p>You want to learn more about how to prepare for a disaster? Or you would like to know how well prepared you already are? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 10 to 15 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>You will now be asked a number of questions e.g. about your previous hazard experience, how you receive hazard-related information and if that leads you to taking preparedness actions.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a short feedback report will provide an overview about factors that</p>	<p>Welcome to the Preparedness-Check for the general public on “Floods”!</p> <p>You want to learn more about how to prepare for a disaster? Or you would like to know how well prepared you already are? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 10 to 15 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>You will now be asked a number of questions e.g. about your previous hazard experience, how you receive hazard-related information and if that leads you to taking preparedness actions.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a short feedback report will provide an overview about factors that shape preparedness, as well as specific</p>	<p>Welcome to the Preparedness-Check for the general public on “Epidemics”</p> <p>You want to learn more about how to prepare for a disaster? Or you would like to know how well prepared you already are? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 10 to 15 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>You will now be asked a number of questions e.g. about your previous hazard experience, how you receive hazard-related information and if that leads you to taking preparedness actions.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a short feedback report will provide an overview about factors that shape</p>	<p>Welcome to the Preparedness-Check for the general public on “Earthquakes”!</p> <p>You want to learn more about how to prepare for a disaster? Or you would like to know how well prepared you already are? Then we welcome you on the TACTIC online platform and ask you to take some time - about 10 to 15 minutes - to answer the next set of questions.</p> <p>You will now be asked a number of questions e.g. about your previous hazard experience, how you receive hazard-related information and if that leads you to taking preparedness actions.</p> <p>Based on your answers, a short feedback report will provide an</p>

	shape preparedness, as well as specific actions to be taken to increase preparedness. It will also provide you with links to documents and websites that might be useful, if you want to learn more.	actions to be taken to increase preparedness. It will also provide you with links to documents and websites that might be useful, if you want to learn more.	actions to be taken to increase preparedness. It will also provide you with links to documents and websites that might be useful, if you want to learn more.	overview about factors that shape preparedness, as well as specific actions to be taken to increase preparedness. It will also provide you with links to documents and websites that might be useful, if you want to learn more.
1	Where do you live? (country)	Where do you live? (country)	Where do you live? (country)	Where do you live? (country)
	We would like to gain a brief overview about how you perceive the risk of terrorism and your involvement in community life.	Now we would like to gain a brief overview about how you perceive flood risk and your involvement in community life.	Now we would like to gain a brief overview about how you perceive epidemic risk and your involvement in community life.	Now we would like to gain a brief overview about how you perceive earthquake risk and your involvement in community life.
2	How much do you feel exposed to the risk of terrorism? 1. Very exposed 2. Exposed 3. Neither exposed nor not exposed 4. Not exposed	How much do you feel exposed to the risk of flooding? 1. Very exposed 2. Exposed 3. Neither exposed nor not exposed 4. Not exposed	How much do you feel exposed to the risk of epidemics? 1. Very exposed 2. Exposed 3. Neither exposed nor not exposed 4. Not exposed	How much do you feel exposed to the risk of earthquakes? 1. Very exposed 2. Exposed 3. Neither exposed nor not exposed 4. Not exposed

	5. Not exposed at all	5. Not exposed at all	5. Not exposed at all	5. Not exposed at all
3	<p>How prepared do you feel for the risk of a future terrorist attack?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very well prepared 2. Prepared 3. Neither prepared nor unprepared 4. Not prepared 5. Not prepared at all 	<p>How prepared do you feel for the risk of future flooding?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very well prepared 2. Prepared 3. Neither prepared nor unprepared 4. Not prepared 5. Not prepared at all 	<p>How prepared do you feel for the risk of future epidemics?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very well prepared 2. Prepared 3. Neither prepared nor unprepared 4. Not prepared 5. Not prepared at all 	<p>How prepared do you feel for the risk of a future earthquake event?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very well prepared 2. Prepared 3. Neither prepared nor unprepared 4. Not prepared 5. Not prepared at all
4	<p>Have you ever personally experienced the negative consequences of a terrorist attack (e.g. disruption to daily life)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No (continue with question 7) 	<p>Have you ever personally experienced the negative consequences of a flood event (e.g. disruption to daily life)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No (continue with question 7) 	<p>Have you ever personally experienced the negative consequences of an epidemic event (e.g. disruption to daily life)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No (continue with question 7) 	<p>Have you ever personally experienced the negative consequences of an earthquake event (e.g. disruption to daily life)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No (continue with question 7)

5	<p>How many times have you experienced a terrorist attack within the last 10 years?</p> <p>a) Once b) Twice c) More than twice d) Never (continue with question 7)</p>	<p>How many times have you experienced a flood event within the last 10 years?</p> <p>a) Once b) Twice c) More than twice d) Never (continue with question 7)</p>	<p>How many times have you or individuals in your community experienced an epidemic event within the last 10 years?</p> <p>a) Once b) Twice c) More than twice d) Never (continue to question 7)</p>	<p>How many times have you experienced an earthquake event within the last 10 years?</p> <p>a) Once b) Twice c) More than twice d) Never (continue with question 7)</p>
6	<p>Did you suffer negative consequences from the terrorist attack? (you may select multiple answers if applicable)</p> <p>a) No b) Yes, I or a family member suffered material damage (to my home, possessions, etc.) c) Yes, I or a family member suffered physical harm (injuries) d) Yes, I or a family member suffered psychological consequences (fear, depression, death in the family/ friend,</p>	<p>Did you suffer negative consequences from a flood event? (you may select multiple answers if applicable)</p> <p>a) No b) Yes, I or a family member suffered material damage (to my home, possessions, etc.) c) Yes, I or a family member suffered physical harm (injuries) d) Yes, I or a family member suffered psychological consequences (fear, depression, death in the family/ friend, etc.) e) Yes, through damaged transportation or supply</p>	<p>Was your experience with epidemics a human disease or zoonotic disease (one that passes from animals to humans such as Avian influenza 'bird flu' or Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS))? (you may select multiple answers if applicable):</p> <p>a) No b) Yes, I or a family member living in my household suffered personally from the disease event from negative health outcomes c) Yes, I or a family member</p>	<p>Did you suffer negative consequences from an earthquake event? (you may select multiple answers if applicable)</p> <p>a) No b) Yes, I or a family member suffered material damage (to my home, possessions, etc.) c) Yes, I or a family member suffered physical harm (injuries/death) d) Yes, I or a family member suffered psychological consequences (fear, anxiety, depression,</p>

	<p>etc.) e) Yes, through damaged transportation or supply infrastructure, etc.</p>	<p>infrastructure, etc.</p>	<p>living in my household, suffered emotional stress (fear, depressions, etc.) as a result of an epidemic</p> <p>d) es, I or a family member living in my household suffered material/economic damage (e.g. business related losses or other employment related loss) as the result of a human disease epidemic</p> <p>e) es, I or a family member living in my household suffered from a disruption of services in the community as a result of the epidemic (e.g. movement bans, quarantine, cancelled public meetings/engagements, restricted transportation, school closures, etc.)</p> <p>Check all that apply for animal disease, e.g. does not affect humans but does affect animals below:</p> <p>a)</p>	<p>grief, etc.) e) Yes, through damaged transportation or supply infrastructure, etc.</p>
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			<p>o</p> <p>b) es, I or a family member living in my household suffered personally from the a disease outbreak as it impacted the family's livestock</p> <p>c) es, I or a family member living in my household, suffered emotional stresses (fear, depressions, etc.) as a result of an epidemic</p> <p>d) es, I or a family member living in my household suffered material/economic damage (e.g. business related losses or other employment related loss) as the result of an animal disease epidemic</p> <p>e) es, I or a family member living in my household suffered from a disruption of services in the community as a result of the epidemic (e.g. movement bans, quarantine, cancelled public</p>	
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			meetings/engagements, restricted transportation, school closures, etc.)	
7	<p>Please describe how often you:</p> <p>a) Think about terrorism b) Talk about terrorism with family and friends</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once a week, or more 2. A few times a month 3. Once a month 4. A few times a year 5. Rarely 6. Never 	<p>Please describe how often you:</p> <p>a) Think about floods b) Talk about floods with family and friends</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once a week, or more 2. A few times a month 3. Once a month 4. A few times a year 5. Rarely 6. Never 	<p>Please describe how often you:</p> <p>a) Think about animal epidemics b) Talk about animal epidemics with family or friends) c) Think about human epidemics d) Talk about human epidemics with family or friends)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once a week, or more 2. A few times a month 3. Once a month 4. A few times a year 5. Rarely 6. Never 	<p>Please describe how often you:</p> <p>a) Think about earthquakes b) Talk about earthquakes with family and friends</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once a week, or more 2. A few times a month 3. Once a month 4. A few times a year 5. Rarely 6. Never

8	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements regarding preparing for a terrorist attack: (please select one answer per line)</p> <p>a) A terrorist attack is too destructive to bother preparing for</p> <p>b) A terrorist attack is unlikely to occur in my community during my lifetime</p> <p>c) Preparing for a terrorist attack is inconvenient for me</p> <p>d) It is difficult to prepare for a terrorist attack</p> <p>e) I don't want to think about preparing for a terrorist attack</p> <p>f) I feel that I/my family are prepared for an a terrorist attack because, we have taken steps to prepare for such an event</p> <p>g) Preparing for terrorism</p>	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements regarding preparation for floods: (please select one answer per line)</p> <p>a) Floods are too destructive to bother preparing for</p> <p>b) a serious flood is unlikely to occur during my lifetime</p> <p>c) Preparing for floods is inconvenient for me</p> <p>d) It is difficult to prepare for floods</p> <p>e) I don't want to think about preparing for a flood event</p> <p>f) I feel that I/my family are prepared for an a flood event because, we have taken steps to prepare for such an event</p> <p>g) Preparing for a flood event makes me feel more at risk of a flood event</p> <p>1. Strongly agree</p> <p>2. Agree</p> <p>3. Neither agree nor disagree</p>	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements regarding preparation for epidemics: (please select one answer per line)</p> <p>a) Epidemics are too destructive to bother preparing for</p> <p>b) A serious epidemic is unlikely to occur during my lifetime</p> <p>c) Preparing for an epidemic is inconvenient for me</p> <p>d) It is difficult to prepare for an epidemic event</p> <p>e) I don't want to think about preparing for an epidemic event</p> <p>f) I feel that I/my family are prepared for an epidemic because, we have taken steps to prepare during a health emergency</p> <p>g) Preparing for a an epidemic event makes me feel more at risk of such an event</p>	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements regarding preparation for earthquakes: (please select one answer per line)</p> <p>a) Earthquakes are too destructive to bother preparing for</p> <p>b) A serious earthquake is unlikely to occur during my lifetime</p> <p>c) Preparing for earthquakes is inconvenient for me</p> <p>d) It is difficult to prepare for earthquakes</p> <p>e) I don't want to think about preparing for an earthquake event</p> <p>f) I feel that I/my family are prepared for an earthquake event because, we have taken steps to prepare for such an event</p> <p>g) Preparing for a an earthquake event makes me feel more at</p>
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	<p>makes me feel more at risk of a terrorist attack</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<p>risk of such an event</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree
9	<p>We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your first thoughts.</p>	<p>We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your first thoughts.</p>	<p>We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your first thoughts.</p>	<p>We are interested in how you perceive the given hazard. The answers that you give will feel subjective but this is the point. Please answer the following questions quickly based on your first thoughts.</p>

	<p>To what extent is the risk of terrorism voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of terrorism) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>	<p>To what extent is the risk of flooding voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of flooding) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>	<p>To what extent is the risk of epidemics voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of epidemics) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>	<p>To what extent is the risk of earthquake voluntary (e.g. do people's choices put them at greater risk of epidemics) or not?</p> <p>1 voluntarily 2 3 4 5 involuntarily</p>
		<p>To what extend is the risk of flooding natural or human-made?</p> <p>1 natural 2 3 4 5 human-made</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of epidemics is natural or human-made?</p> <p>1 natural 2 3 4 5 human-made</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of an earthquake event natural or human-made?</p> <p>1 natural 2 3 4 5 human-made</p>
	<p>To what extend is the risk of terrorism threatening or unthreatening?</p> <p>1 threatening 2 3 4</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of flooding threatening or unthreatening?</p> <p>1 threatening 2 3 4</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of epidemics threatening or unthreatening?</p> <p>1 threatening 2 3 4</p>	<p>To what extend is the risk of an earthquake event threatening or unthreatening?</p> <p>1 threatening 2 3 4</p>

	5 unthreatening	5 unthreatening	5 unthreatening	5 unthreatening
	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of terrorism? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of flooding? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of epidemics? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar	How familiar or unfamiliar is the risk of an earthquake? 1 familiar 2 3 4 5 unfamiliar
	To what extent is the risk of terrorism manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable	To what extent is risk of flooding manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable	To what extent is the epidemic risk manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable	To what extent is the risk of an earthquake event manageable or unmanageable? 1 manageable 2 3 4 5 unmanageable
		To what extent is the risk of flooding distributed fairly or unfairly among members of society? 1 fairly 2 3 4 5 unfairly	To what extent is the risk of epidemics distributed fairly or unfairly among members of society? 1 fairly 2 3 4 5 unfairly	To what extent is the risk of earthquakes distributed fairly or unfairly among members of society? 1 fairly 2 3 4 5 unfairly

		<p>To what extend is the knowledge about the community's risk of flooding scientifically certain or uncertain?</p> <p>1 certain 2 3 4 5 uncertain</p>	<p>To what extend is the knowledge about the community's risk of an epidemic event scientifically certain or uncertain?</p> <p>1 certain 2 3 4 5 uncertain</p>	<p>To what extend is the knowledge about the community's risk of an earthquake event scientifically certain or uncertain?</p> <p>1 certain 2 3 4 5 uncertain</p>
	<p>Now we have some more general questions not directly related to the risk of terrorism</p>	<p>Now we have some more general questions not directly related to flood risks</p>	<p>Now we have some more general questions not directly related to epidemic risks, but which help to understand how you approach problem solving on your own and in your community</p>	<p>Now we have some more general questions not directly related to earthquake risks</p>
10	<p>To what extent do you agree that the opinions of the following people are important to you when deciding on a particular course of action?</p> <p>a. Opinions of my family b. Opinions of my friends c. Opinions of my neighbours/community d. Opinions of local public</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree that the opinions of the following people are important to you when deciding on a particular course of action?</p> <p>a. Opinions of my family b. Opinions of my friends c. Opinions of my neighbours/community d. Opinions of local public authorities</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree that the opinions of the following people are important to you when deciding on a particular course of action?</p> <p>a. Opinions of my family b. Opinions of my friends c. Opinions of my neighbours/community d. Opinions of local public</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree that the opinions of the following people are important to you when deciding on a particular course of action?</p> <p>a. Opinions of my family b. Opinions of my friends c. Opinions of my neighbours/community d. Opinions of my public</p>

	<p>authorities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very Important 2. Important 3. Neither important nor 4. Unimportant 5. Very unimportant 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very Important 2. Important 3. Neither important nor 4. Unimportant 5. Very unimportant 	<p>authorities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very Important 2. Important 3. Neither important nor 4. Unimportant 5. Very unimportant 	<p>authorities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very Important 2. Important 3. Neither important nor 4. Unimportant 5. Very unimportant
11	<p>In regard to your general feelings about living in your community, please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. I trust that responsible state agencies authorities will keep me informed about changes in the terrorism threat level b. I trust that responsible state agencies will take my worries seriously regarding potential terrorist attacks c. I trust that responsible state agencies are taking the necessary prevention and preparedness measures before a terrorist attack occurs d. I trust that responsible 	<p>In regard to your general feelings about living in your community, please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. I trust that responsible state agencies will inform me before a flood strikes my community b. I trust that responsible state agencies will take my worries and needs seriously regarding potential floods c. I trust that responsible state agencies will take necessary mitigation measures before a flood strikes d. I trust that responsible state agencies are able to help me in an emergency situation. e. I trust that responsible state agencies are interested in my 	<p>In regard to your general feelings about living in your community, please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. I trust that responsible state agencies will inform me before an epidemic threat occurs in my community b. I trust that responsible state agencies will take my worries and needs seriously regarding potential epidemics c. I trust that responsible state agencies will take necessary preparation measures before an epidemic strikes d. I trust that responsible state agencies are able to 	<p>In regard to your general feelings about living in your community, please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. I trust that responsible state agencies will inform me about earthquake risks for my community b. I trust that responsible state agencies will take my worries and needs seriously regarding potential earthquakes c. I trust that responsible state agencies will take necessary mitigation measures before an earthquake strikes d. I trust that responsible state agencies are able

	<p>state agencies are able to help me in the event of a terrorist attack.</p> <p>e. I trust that government authorities are interested in my involvement in preparedness activities for terrorism (e.g. participation in exercises)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<p>collaboration (e.g. participation in formal hearings or other collaborative opportunities)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<p>help me in an emergency situation.</p> <p>e. I trust that responsible state agencies are interested in my collaboration (e.g. participation in formal hearings or other collaborative opportunities)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<p>to help me in an emergency situation.</p> <p>e. I trust that responsible state agencies are interested in my collaboration (e.g. participation in formal hearings or other collaborative opportunities)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. disagree 5. Strongly disagree
	<p>Now we would like to know about where you get your information about the risk of terrorism from and what you think about it</p>	<p>Now we would like to know about where you get your information about flood risks from and what you think about it</p>	<p>Now we would like to know about where you get your information about epidemic risks from and what you think about it</p>	<p>Now we would like to know about where you get your information about earthquake risks from and what you think about it</p>
12	<p>Have you informed yourself in the past about the risk of terrorism in your community?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (proceed with question 19)</p>	<p>Have you informed yourself in the past about the risk of flooding in your community?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (proceed with question 19)</p>	<p>Have you informed yourself in the past about the risk of epidemics in your community?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (proceed with question 19)</p>	<p>Have you informed yourself in the past about the risk of an earthquake event in your community?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No (proceed with question 19)</p>

13	<p>What were the main reasons (you may select multiple answers if applicable)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) I wanted to know more about the risk of terrorism b) I wanted to learn more about what I can do to reduce my personal risk of future terrorist attacks c) I wanted to know more about how exposed I am personally to a terrorist attack d) I wanted to learn more about my responsibilities in relation to preparing for terrorism e) I wanted to learn more about how I can participate in activities organised by local government designed to prepare for terrorism (e.g., community 	<p>What were the main reasons (you may select multiple answers if applicable)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) I wanted to know more about the flood risk b) I wanted to learn more about what I can do to reduce my personal flood risk c) I wanted to know how exposed my house is to the risk of flooding d) I wanted to learn more about my responsibilities in flood risk management e) I wanted to learn more about how I can participate in decision-making processes in flood risk management f) There is a conflict in our community with regard to flood risks and I wanted to gather more information about it g) Other reasons 	<p>What were the main reasons (you may select multiple answers if applicable)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) I wanted to know more about the epidemic risk b) I wanted to learn more about what I can do to reduce my personal epidemic risk c) I wanted to know more about how exposed I am individually to the risk of an epidemic event d) I wanted to learn more about my responsibilities in epidemic risk management e) I wanted to learn more about how I can participate in decision-making processes in epidemic risk management f) There is a conflict in our community with regard to epidemic risks and I wanted to gather more 	<p>What were the main reasons (you may select multiple answers if applicable)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) I wanted to know more about this risk b) I wanted to learn more about what I can do to reduce my personal earthquake risk c) I wanted to know how exposed my house is to the risk of an earthquake event d) I wanted to learn more about my responsibilities in earthquake risk management e) I wanted to learn more about how I can participate in decision-making processes in earthquake risk management f) There is a conflict in our

	<p>meetings, exercises)</p> <p>f) There is a conflict in our community with regards to the risk of terrorism and I wanted to gather more information</p> <p>g) Other reasons</p>		<p>information about it</p> <p>g) Other reasons</p>	<p>community with regard to earthquake risks and I wanted to gather more information about it</p> <p>g) Other reasons</p>
14	<p>From whom did you receive the information about the risk of terrorism?</p> <p>d) National agencies</p> <p>e) Regional agencies</p> <p>f) Local agencies</p> <p>g) Family/Friends/Neighbours</p> <p>h) The media</p> <p>i) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters)</p> <p>j) Civic associations</p> <p>k) Others</p>	<p>From whom did you receive the information about the risk of flooding?</p> <p>a) National agencies</p> <p>b) Regional agencies</p> <p>c) Local agencies</p> <p>d) Family/Friends/Neighbours</p> <p>e) The media</p> <p>f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters)</p> <p>g) Civic associations</p> <p>h) Others</p>	<p>From whom did you receive the information about the risk of epidemics?</p> <p>a) National agencies</p> <p>b) Regional agencies</p> <p>c) Local agencies</p> <p>d) Friends/Neighbours</p> <p>e) The media</p> <p>f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters)</p> <p>g) Civic associations</p> <p>h) Others</p>	<p>From whom did you receive the information about the risk of earthquakes?</p> <p>d) National agencies</p> <p>e) Regional agencies</p> <p>f) Local agencies</p> <p>g) Friends/Neighbours</p> <p>h) The media</p> <p>i) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters)</p> <p>j) Civic associations</p> <p>k) Others</p>
15	<p>How trustful do you consider the actors that you received the information from?</p> <p>a) National agencies</p> <p>b) Regional agencies</p>	<p>How trustful do you consider the actors that you received the information from?</p> <p>a) National agencies</p> <p>b) Regional agencies</p>	<p>How trustful do you consider the actors that you received the information from?</p> <p>a) National agencies</p> <p>b) Regional agencies</p>	<p>How trustful do you consider the actors that you received the information from?</p> <p>a) National agencies</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations h) Others <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very trustful 2. Trustful 3. Neither trustful nor untrustful 4. Not trustful 5. Very untrustful 6. Does not apply 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations h) Others <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very trustful 2. Trustful 3. Neither trustful nor untrustful 4. Not trustful 5. Very untrustful 6. Does not apply 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations h) Others <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very trustful 2. Trustful 3. Neither trustful nor untrustful 4. Not trustful 5. Very untrustful 6. Does not apply 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) Regional agencies c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations h) Others <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very trustful 2. Trustful 3. Neither trustful nor untrustful 4. Not trustful 5. Very untrustful 6. Does not apply
16	<p>Has your trust in the actors changed over the last 10 years/since the last terrorist attack?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) National agencies b) Regional agencies c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations 	<p>Has your trust in the actors changed over the last 10 years/since the last event?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) National agencies b) Regional agencies c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations h) Others 	<p>Has your trust in the actors changed over the last 10 years/since the last event?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) National agencies b) Regional agencies c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations h) Others 	<p>Has your trust in the actors changed over the last 10 years/since the last event?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) National agencies b) Regional agencies c) Local agencies d) Family/Friends/Neighbours e) The media f) Relief organisations (e.g. fire fighters) g) Civic associations h) Others

	<p>h) Others</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes, it improved 2. No 3. Yes, it worsened 4. Does not apply 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes, it improved 2. No 3. Yes, it worsened 4. Does not apply 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes, it improved 2. No 3. Yes, it worsened 4. Does not apply 	
17	<p>How often do you use the following sources of information in order to obtain information about the risk of terrorism?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b) Newspaper c) Online news d) Radio e) Social media f) Television g) Training course h) Workshops or public meetings i) SMS from emergency services j) Others [...] <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once a week, or more 2. A few times a month 3. Once a month 4. A few times a year 5. Rarely 	<p>How often do you use the following sources of information in order to obtain information about the risk of flooding?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b. Newspaper c. Online news d. Radio e. Social media f. Television g. Videotext h. Floods Centres i. Risk maps j. Tour or demonstration (field trip) k. Training course l. Workshops or public meetings m. SMS from 	<p>How often do you use the following sources of information in order to obtain information about the risk of epidemics?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b) Newspaper c) Online news d) Healthcare centre e) Radio f) Social media g) Television h) Risk maps i) tour or demonstration (field trip) j) Training course k) Workshops or public meetings l) SMS from emergency services m) Others [...] <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once a week, or more 2. A few times a month 	<p>How often do you use the following sources of information in order to obtain information about the risk of earthquakes?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b) Newspaper c) Online news d) Earthquake Centre e) Radio f) Social media g) Television h) Risk maps i) Tour or demonstration (field trip) j) Training course k) Workshops or public meetings l) SMS from emergency services m) Others [...]

	6. Never	emergency services n. Others [...]	3. Once a month 4. A few times a year 5. Rarely 6. Never	1. Once a week, or more 2. A few times a month 3. Once a month 4. A few times a year 5. Rarely 6. Never
18	<p>Which source of information would you like to use more often in order to obtain information about the risk of terrorism?</p> <p>a) Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b) Newspaper c) Online news d) Radio e) Social media f) Television g) Training course h) Workshops or public meetings i) SMS from emergency services j) Others [...]</p>	<p>Which source of information would you like to use more often in order to obtain information about the risk of flood?</p> <p>a. Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b. Newspaper c. Online news d. Radio e. Social media f. Television g. Videotext h. Floods Centres i. Risk maps j. Tour or demonstration (field trip) k. Training course l. Workshops or public meetings m. SMS from emergency services n. Others [...]</p>	<p>Which source of information would you like to use more often in order to obtain information about the risk of epidemics?</p> <p>a) Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b) Newspaper c) Online news d) Healthcare centre e) Radio f) Social media g) Television h) Risk maps i) tour or demonstration (field trip) j) Training course k) Workshops or public meetings l) SMS from emergency services m) Others [...]</p>	<p>Which source of information would you like to use more often in order to obtain information about the risk earthquake?</p> <p>a) Discussions with neighbours, friends and family b) Newspaper c) Online news d) Earthquake Centre e) Radio f) Social media g) Television h) Risk maps i) Tour or demonstration (field trip) j) Training course k) Workshops or public meetings l) SMS from emergency services</p>

				m) Others [...]
19	<p>Have you been involved in activities organised by local government designed to prepare for terrorism (e.g., community meetings, exercises)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No, but I would like to become involved c) No, I am not interested</p>	<p>Have you been involved in decision-making processes in flood risk management (e.g. planning of flood protection measures)?</p> <p>a) Yes b) No, but I would like to become involved c) No, I am not interested</p>	<p>Have you ever been involved in a planning event in your community such as planning to provide seasonal flu vaccines, campaigns or events to raise awareness of household/community emergency planning measures, etc.?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No, but I would like to become involved c. No, I am not interested</p>	<p>Have you been involved in decision-making processes in earthquake risk management (e.g. planning of earthquake protection and mitigation measures)?</p> <p>a. Yes b. No, but I would like to become involved c. No, I am not interested</p>
20		<p>Have you been involved in a training exercise in your community for flood preparedness? For example, some communities have emergency simulations for flood events. Other communities may have first aid training or family emergency planning sessions for preparing for flood events</p> <p>a) Yes b) No, but I would like to become involved c) No, I am not interested</p>	<p>Have you been involved in a training exercise in your community for epidemic preparedness? For example, some communities have emergency simulations for animal disease outbreaks. Other communities may have first aid training or household/community emergency planning sessions for preparing for human disease epidemics</p> <p>a. Yes b. No, but I would like to become involved c. No, I am not interested</p>	<p>Have you been involved in a training exercise in your community for earthquake preparedness? For example, some communities have emergency simulations for earthquake events. Other communities may have first aid training or family emergency planning sessions for preparing for earthquake events</p> <p>a. Yes b. No, but I would like to become involved c. No, I am not interested</p>

	Now, we would like to know which actions you have taken to prevent or prepare for a terrorist attack or you are planning to take in the future and why?	Now, we would like to know which preparedness actions you have taken or you are planning to take in the future and why?	Now, we would like to know which preparedness actions you have taken or that you are planning to take in the future and why?	Now, we would like to know which preparedness actions you have taken or you are planning to take in the future and why?
21	<p>What do you think, to what extent are you able to reduce the impact of a terrorist attack through your own actions and decisions?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To a very large extent 2. To a large extent 3. Neither nor 4. Not 5. Not at all 	<p>What do you think, to what extent are you able to reduce the impact of a flood event through your own actions and decisions?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To a very large extent 2. To a large extent 3. Neither nor 4. Not 5. Not at all 	<p>What do you think, to what extent are you able to reduce the impact of an epidemic event through your own actions and decisions?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To a very large extent 2. To a large extent 3. Neither nor 4. Not 5. Not at all 	<p>What do you think, to what extent are you able to reduce the impact of an earthquake through your own actions and decisions?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To a very large extent 2. To a large extent 3. Neither nor 4. Not 5. Not at all
22	<p>Have you taken any of the following measures to prepare yourself for a terrorist attack? (you may select multiple answers if applicable)</p>	<p>Have you taken any of the following measures to prepare yourself for a flood? (you may select multiple answers if applicable)</p>	<p>Have you taken any of the following measures to prepare yourself for a human disease epidemic? (you may select multiple answers if applicable)</p>	<p>Have you taken any of the following measures to prepare yourself for an earthquake? (you may select multiple answers if applicable)</p>
	<p>a) Have you studied actions that can be taken to prevent a terrorist attack (e.g. reporting suspicious activity)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't know that a 	<p>a) Have you studied flood maps to know your flood risk?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I was not aware of the existence of flood maps ii. I don't know 		<p>a) Have you studied seismic risk (earthquake) maps to know your risk?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I was not aware of the

	<p>terrorist attack could be prevented</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii. I haven't had the time iii. I have no interest iv. Psychologically, I don't want to think about terrorism 	<p>how to access them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> iii. I haven't had the time to look for them iv. I have no interest v. I don't feel comfortable reading a map 		<p>existence of earthquake maps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii. I don't know how to access them iii. I haven't had the time to look for them iv. I have no interest v. I don't feel comfortable reading a map
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		<p>b) Do you have flood insurance?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why?</p> <p> i. Insurance is not available</p> <p> ii. I tried to get one, but didn't get one</p> <p> iii. They are too expensive</p> <p> iv. I had one but cancelled it</p> <p> v. I had one, but it was cancelled by the insurance company</p> <p> vi. I don't need one</p>	<p>a) Do you have insurance against epidemic-related damages (e.g. health insurance, farm/business insurance, epidemic insurance)?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why not?</p> <p> i. Insurance is not available</p> <p> ii. I tried to obtain an insurance plan, but was unable</p> <p> iii. Plans are too expensive</p> <p> iv. I had one but cancelled it</p> <p> v. It was cancelled by the insurance company</p> <p> vi. I don't need one</p>	<p>b) Do you have earthquake insurance?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why?</p> <p> i. Insurance is not available</p> <p> ii. I tried to obtain an insurance plan, but was unable</p> <p> iii. Plans are too expensive</p> <p> iv. I had one but cancelled it</p> <p> v. It was cancelled by the insurance company</p> <p> vi. I don't need</p>
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	<p>b) Have you created an emergency kit specifically for terrorism?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why?</p> <p> i. I don't have the time</p> <p> ii. I don't think that such a kit will make a difference</p> <p> iii. I don't know what to put in such a kit</p> <p> iv. I don't want to</p>	<p>c) Do you have an emergency kit for a flood event?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why?</p> <p> i. I don't have the time</p> <p> ii. I don't think that such a kit will make a difference</p> <p> iii. I don't know what to put in such a kit</p> <p> iv. I don't want to engage with preparing for a flood event</p> <p> v. I don't have the financial resources to</p>	<p>b) Do you have an emergency kit (e.g. it includes any of the following: medical supplies, a radio to receive emergency warnings, prescription medications for myself/my family, over the counter medications, electrolytes, cleaning & disinfecting supplies, batteries, I know where I store important documents, emergency supplies, medicines, phone numbers ready, evacuation procedures)?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why not?</p> <p> i. I don't have the time</p> <p> ii. I don't think that such a kit will make a difference</p>	<p>c) Do you have an emergency kit for earthquakes?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why?</p> <p> i. I don't have the time</p> <p> ii. I don't think that such a kit will make a difference</p> <p> iii. I don't know what to put in such a kit</p>

	engage with preparing for a terrorist attack v. I don't have the financial resources to build such a kit	build such a kit	iii. I don't know what to put in such a kit iv. I don't want to engage with preparing for an epidemic event v. I don't have the financial resources to build such a kit	iv. I don't want to engage with preparing for an earthquake event v. I don't have the financial resources to build such a kit
	<p>c) Do you have an emergency plan specifically covering terrorism?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No If no, why?</p> <p>i. I don't have the time ii. I don't think that such a plan will</p>	<p>d) Do you have a Flood Emergency Plan?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No If no, why?</p> <p>i. I don't have the time ii. I don't think that such a plan will make a difference iii. I don't know</p>	<p>c) Do you have an epidemic emergency plan for your family, small business or farm (e.g. I have a 'flu buddy' to get medications or supplies for me when I am sick, I have made plans for how to take care of a sick member of my household or for those I look after in the community, and/or I developed a farm health care plan, etc.)?</p>	<p>d) Do you have an earthquake emergency and evacuation plan?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No If no, why?</p> <p>i. I don't have the time ii. I don't think that</p>

	<p>make a difference</p> <p>iii. I don't know how to develop such a plan</p> <p>iv. I don't want to engage with preparing for a terrorist attack</p>	<p>how to develop such a plan</p> <p>iv. I don't want to engage with preparing for a flood event</p>	<p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why not?</p> <p> i. I don't have the time</p> <p> ii. I don't think that such a plan will make a difference</p> <p> iii. I don't know how to develop such a plan</p> <p> iv. I don't want to engage with preparing for an epidemic event</p>	<p>such a plan will make a difference</p> <p>iii. I don't know how to develop such a plan</p> <p>iv. I don't want to engage with preparing for an earthquake</p>
			<p>d) Do you know about infectious disease control measures and policies (e.g. I get vaccinated when disease threats are identified in my community and vaccines are available, I have diversified my farm business portfolio, I am a member of a livestock scheme or other groups that</p>	

			<p>enable members to discuss and learn about biosecurity, farm health concerns, and/or engage in other preparedness plans etc.)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why not? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I don't know where to access them ii. I haven't had the time to look for them iii. I am not concerned about potential negative health outcomes (e.g. stress over injections, concern over vaccination , other concerns) 	
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			iv. I don't feel that this is a good way to prepare	
	<p>d) Did you look at the instructions/advice from local/regional/national government on how to respond to a terrorist attack?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why?</p> <p> i. I don't want to think about terrorism</p> <p> ii. I didn't know that this information was available</p> <p> iii. This information is not provided</p> <p> iv. I don't have the time to do this</p>		<p>e) Do you know what to do during an epidemic event (practise good hand hygiene, avoiding crowds, public transportation or other public gatherings during an epidemic warning or an epidemic, etc.)?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why not?</p> <p> i. I don't know where to gain information on these activities</p> <p> ii. This information is not provided</p> <p> iii. I haven't had the time to inform myself</p>	

	<p>v. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this</p>		<p>iv. I am not concerned about the risk of epidemics</p>	
	<p>e) Did you take security measures to protect yourself / your family from a cyber-terrorism attack?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No If no, why?</p> <p> i. I don't know what cyber-terrorism is</p> <p> vi. I didn't know that you can prevent cyber-terrorism</p> <p> vii. I don't have the time to do this</p> <p> viii. I don't see any benefit/v</p>			

	alue in doing this			
				<p>e) Do you have a family reunion plan (e.g., identifying a common meeting place to come together after a possible earthquake)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I don't have the time ii. I don't think that such a plan will make a difference iii. I don't know how to develop such a plan
		<p>e) Did you elevate the furnace, water heater and electrical panel because you live in an area of high flood risk?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. The building was already constructed in a flood-safe manner ii. I didn't know that this was 		<p>f) Did you arrange all the furniture in your home so that they are not next to the windows and they will not block the escape routes?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't need to because they were already arranged before I moved in

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> iii. something that I should do iv. I don't have the financial resources to do this v. I don't have the time to do this vi. I don't see the benefit/value of doing this 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii. I didn't know that this was something that I should do iii. I don't have the time to do this iv. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this
		<p>f) Have you installed "check valves" to prevent flood water from backing up into the drains?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Yes ii. No If no, why? iii. I didn't know about them iv. I don't know where to access them v. I don't have the financial resources to do this vi. I haven't had the time to install them vii. I don't see any benefit/value of doing this 		<p>g) Have you secured items that could fall and cause injuries (e.g., bookshelves, mirrors, etc.) because you live in an area of high earthquake risk?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. All of my moveable belongings were already secured before I moved in ii. I am a tenant, my landlord won't permit me to make changes iii. I don't know how to secure items iv. I don't have the financial resources to do this v. I don't have the time to do this vi. I don't see the benefit/value of doing this

		<p>g) Have you sealed walls in the basement with waterproofing compounds?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't need to because they were already built before I moved in ii. I don't know who to contact to help me to do this iii. I don't have the financial resources to do this iv. I don't have the time to do this v. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this. 		
		<p>h) Have you changed floor material on the ground floor to be water resistant?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why not? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't need to because they were already built before I moved in ii. I don't know who to contact to help me to do this iii. I don't have the financial resources to do this iv. I don't have the time to do this 		<p>h) Have you identified the location of the switches for water, gas, and electric power?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't know that this was something that I should do ii. I don't know where to access them iii. I haven't had the time to look for them iv. I don't see any benefit/value of doing

		v. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this		this
		<p>i) Have you constructed barriers (concrete walls / earth levees) to stop floodwater from entering the building</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No If no, why?</p> <p>i. I didn't need to because they were already built before I moved in ii. I don't know who to contact to help me to do this iii. I don't have the financial resources to do this iv. I don't have the time to do this v. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this</p>		<p>i) Have you assessed your home and/or your business building for earthquake resistance according to building codes?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No If no, why?</p> <p>i. A serious earthquake is unlikely to occur during my lifetime ii. I don't know who to contact to help me to do this iii. I don't trust assessment firms or procedures iv. Earthquakes are too destructive to bother preparing for v. I don't have the financial resources to do this vi. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this</p>
		j) Have you prepared mobile		j) Have you retrofitted your

		<p>barriers on basement/ground floor windows and doors?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't need to because they were already built before I moved in ii. I don't know who to contact to help me to do this iii. I don't have the financial resources to do this iv. I don't have the time to do this v. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this 		<p>home and/or business building structurally?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't need to because it was already retrofitted ii. I don't know who to contact to help me to do this iii. I don't have the financial resources for retrofitting iv. I don't have the time to do this v. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this vi. I am a renter; I am not responsible for structural retrofitting.
		<p>k) Have you implemented water drainage systems around the house (drainage pipes, rain garden, retention basin, etc.)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? 		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't need to because they were already built before I moved in ii. I don't know who to contact to help me to do this iii. I don't have the financial resources to do this iv. I don't have the time to do this v. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this 		
				<p>k) Have you identified safe places to go to in case of an earthquake (e.g., under a sturdy piece of furniture or against an interior wall in home, office or school)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn't know that this was something that I should do ii. A serious earthquake is unlikely to occur during my lifetime iii. I don't have the time to do this iv. I don't see any benefit/value in doing this

				<p>I) Have you practiced what to do during and immediately after an earthquake (e.g., “Drop, Cover, and Hold On”)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No If no, why? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. I didn’t know that this was something that I should do ii. Earthquakes are too destructive to bother preparing for iii. A serious earthquake is unlikely to occur during my lifetime iv. Preparing for earthquakes is inconvenient for me v. I don’t see any benefit/value in doing this
23	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements : (please select one answer per line)</p> <p>a) Preparing for terrorism will enable me to take some control during the</p>	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements : (please select one answer per line)</p> <p>a) Preparing for floods will significantly reduce the damage to my home should</p>	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements: (please select one answer per line).</p> <p>a) Preparing for epidemics will improve my everyday living conditions</p>	<p>Please describe the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements: (please select one answer per line)</p> <p>a) Preparing for earthquakes will significantly reduce the</p>

	<p>uncertainty of an attack</p> <p>b) Preparing for terrorism will significantly improve my ability to respond effectively to an attack</p> <p>c) Preparing for terrorism will significantly improve my ability to deal with the consequences of a terrorist attack (e.g., psychological impact, physical impact)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<p>a flood occur</p> <p>b) Preparing for floods will improve my everyday living conditions</p> <p>c) Preparing for floods will improve the value of my house/property and helps protecting my equipment</p> <p>d) Preparing for floods will significantly improve my ability to deal with disruption to family/ community life following a flood</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<p>b) Preparing for epidemics will improve my and/or my family's chances for survival during an epidemic</p> <p>c) Preparing for epidemics will significantly improve my ability to deal with disruption to family/ community life following an epidemic</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree 	<p>damage to my home or injury/death should an earthquake occur</p> <p>b) Preparing for earthquakes will improve my everyday living conditions</p> <p>c) Preparing for earthquakes will improve the value of my house/property</p> <p>d) Preparing for earthquakes will significantly improve my ability to deal with disruption to family/ community life following an earthquake</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree
24	If your community experienced a terrorist attack tomorrow what would you do?	If a flood warning was to be issued tomorrow what would you do?	If an epidemic warning was to be issued tomorrow what would you do?	
24.1	I would inform myself about the risk of an attack by:	I would inform myself about the risk of a flood by:	I would inform myself about the risk of an epidemic by:	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Listening to the radio b) Checking the Internet regularly c) Speaking to my neighbour(s), family, friends d) Watching television for updates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Listening to the radio b) Checking the Internet regularly c) Speaking to my neighbour(s), family, friends d) Wait and see if it looks like it is going to flood e) Watching television for updates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Listening to the radio b) Checking the Internet regularly c) Speaking to my neighbour(s), family, friends d) Considering risk associated with travel plans e) Watching television for updates f) Other please specify 	
24.2	<p>What would you do after a terrorist attack?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) I would immediately leave the area b) I would contact friends/family to confirm my safety c) I would contact friends/family to check that they were safe d) I would check for information from local authorities/experts e) I would volunteer to support the response (e.g., donating blood) f) I would seek psychological assistance 	<p>I would prepare myself/my family/belongings by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Leaving as soon as possible b) Moving valuables to upper floors c) Checking if other people in my household require help d) Waiting to be evacuated e) Disconnecting electrical appliances <p>Moving pets / livestock to safe place</p>	<p>I would prepare myself/my family/belongings by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Leaving public areas to return home as soon as possible b) Checking if other people in household require help c) Waiting for instructions from local or national authorities d) Watching television for updates e) Other please specify 	

	Finally, we would like to ask you some information about yourself	Finally, we would like to ask you some information about yourself	Finally, we would like to ask you some information about yourself	Finally, we would like to ask you some information about yourself
25	Gender Male Female I do not wish to declare	Gender Male Female I do not wish to declare	Gender Male Female I do not wish to declare	Gender Male Female I do not wish to declare
26	Age a) Younger than 14 b) 14-25 c) 26-35 d) 36-45 e) 46-55 f) 56-65 g) Older than 65	Age a) Younger than 14 b) 14-25 c) 26-35 d) 36-45 e) 46-55 f) 56-65 g) Older than 65	Age a) Younger than 14 b) 14-25 c) 26-35 d) 36-45 e) 46-55 f) 56-65 g) Older than 65	Age a) Younger than 14 b) 14-25 c) 26-35 d) 36-45 e) 46-55 f) 56-65 g) Older than 65
27	The house/apartment I am living in is: a) My property b) Property of relatives c) Rented d) Other	The house/apartment I am living in is: a) My property b) Property of relatives c) Rented d) Other	The house/apartment/flat that I am living in is: a) My property b) Property of relatives c) Rented d) Other	The house/apartment I am living in is: a) My property b) Property of relatives c) Rented d) Other

28	<p>How many people (including you) live in the household in total?</p> <p>__ Adults (over 18)</p>	<p>How many people (including you) live in the household in total?</p> <p>__ Adults (over 18)</p>	<p>How many people (including you) live in the household in total?</p> <p>__ Adults (over 18)</p>	<p>How many people (including you) live in the household in total?</p> <p>__ Adults (over 18)</p>
29	<p>How many children live in the household?</p> <p>__ Children (under 18)</p>	<p>How many children live in the household?</p> <p>__ Children (under 18)</p>	<p>How many children live in the household?</p> <p>__ Children (under 18)</p>	<p>How many children live in the household?</p> <p>__ Children (under 18)</p>
30	<p>How many people with a disability (physical or mental health problem) or special needs (e.g. non-native speakers, learning disabilities) live in your household?</p> <p>__ people with special needs or a disability people with lower language proficiency (e.g. non-native speakers who may require some assistance with translating warnings or advice regarding a hazard threat)</p>	<p>How many people with a disability (physical or mental) or special needs (e.g. non-native speakers, learning disabilities) live in your household?</p> <p>__ people with special needs or a disability people with lower language proficiency (e.g. non-native speakers who may require some assistance with translating warnings or advice regarding a hazard threat)</p>	<p>How many people with a disability (physical or mental) or special needs (e.g. non-native speakers, learning disabilities) live in your household?</p> <p>__ people with special needs or a disability people with lower language proficiency (e.g. non-native speakers who may require some assistance with translating warnings or advice regarding a hazard threat)</p>	<p>How many people with a disability (physical or mental) or special needs (e.g. non-native speakers, learning disabilities) live in your household?</p> <p>__ people with special needs or a disability people with lower language proficiency (e.g. non-native speakers who may require some assistance with translating warnings or advice regarding a hazard threat)</p>
31	<p>What is your highest degree in formal education?</p> <p>a) No formal education b) Completed Primary</p>	<p>What is your highest degree in formal education?</p> <p>a) No formal education b) Completed Primary</p>	<p>What is your highest degree in formal education?</p> <p>a) No formal education b) Completed Primary</p>	<p>What is your highest degree in formal education?</p> <p>a) No formal education b) Completed Primary</p>

	Education c) Completed Secondary Education d) Technical/Vocational Certificate e) University degree f) Postgraduate qualification g) Still in education	Education c) Completed Secondary Education d) Technical/Vocational Certificate e) University degree f) Postgraduate qualification g) Still in education	Education c) Completed Secondary Education d) Technical/Vocational Certificate e) University degree f) Postgraduate qualification g) Still in education	Education c) Completed Secondary Education d) Technical/Vocational Certificate e) University degree f) Postgraduate qualification g) Still in education
32	What is your occupational status? a) Employed b) Self-Employed c) Unemployed d) Retired e) Stay at home parent f) Student	What is your occupational status? a) Employed b) Self-Employed c) Unemployed d) Retired e) Stay at home parent f) Student	What is your occupational status? a) Employed b) Self-Employed c) Unemployed d) Retired e) Stay at home parent f) Student	What is your occupational status? a) Employed b) Self-Employed c) Unemployed d) Retired e) Homemaker f) Student
33	Are you a member of an association, such as a sports club, religious organisation (e.g. church, mosque, temple, etc.), volunteering organisation or other clubs in your community? a) Yes b) No	Are you a member of an association, such as a sports club, religious organisation (e.g. church, mosque, temple, etc.), volunteering organisation or other clubs in your community? a) Yes b) No	Are you a member of an association, such as a sports club, religious organisation (e.g. church, mosque, temple, etc.), volunteering organisation or other clubs in your community? a) Yes b) No	Are you a member of an association, such as a sports club, religious organisation (e.g. church, mosque, temple, etc.), volunteering organisation or other clubs in your community? a) Yes b) No
	Thank you for your participation I would like to conduct another	Thank you for your participation I would like to conduct another self-	Thank you for your participation I would like to conduct another	Thank you for your participation

	self-assessment [display boxes and exit option]	assessment [display boxes and exit option]	self-assessment [display boxes and exit option]	I would like to conduct another self-assessment [display boxes and exit option]
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References

- Becker, J. S., Paton, D., Johnston, D. M., & Ronan, K. R. (2012). A model of household preparedness for earthquakes: how individuals make meaning of earthquake information and how this influences preparedness. *Natural hazards*, 64(1), 107-137.
- Begg C., Walker G., Kuhlicke C., 2015. Localism and flood risk management in England: the creation of new inequalities? *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy* advance online publication, doi:10.1068/c12216.
- Begg, C., Müller, A., Karanci, N., Doğulu, C., Konieczny, R., Walczykiewicz, T., Siudak, M., Madej, P., Shreve, C., Kuhlicke, C. & C. Mante (2015) D3.1 First Outline of the Report on Communication and Education Material and Practices. Report of the TACTIC Project. Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Leipzig.
- Blaikie, P., Cannon, T., Davis, I., & Wisner, B. (1994). *At risk. Natural hazards, people's vulnerability and disasters*. Routledge US.
- Brewer, N. T., Weinstein, N. D., Cuite, C. L., & Herrington Jr, J. E. (2004). Risk perceptions and their relation to risk behavior. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, 27(2), 125-130.
- Collins, T. W. (2008). The political ecology of hazard vulnerability: marginalization, facilitation and the production of differential risk to urban wildfires in Arizona's White Mountains. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 15(1), 21-43.
- Covello, V. T., et al. (1987) In *Uncertainty in risk assessment, risk management, and decision making*, Springer, p. 172
- Covello, V. T., Peters, R. G., Wojtecki, J. G., & Hyde, R. C. (2001). Risk communication, the West Nile virus epidemic, and bioterrorism: responding to the communication challenges posed by the intentional or unintentional release of a pathogen in an urban setting. *Journal of Urban Health*, 78(2), 382-391.
- Covello, V., & Sandman, P. M. (2001). Risk communication: evolution and revolution. *Solutions to an Environment in Peril*, 164-178.
- EPA, 2012: *Communication Strategies* (accessed 26.01.2015) URL: <http://www.epa.gov/superfund/community/pdfs/toolkit/comstrats.pdf>
- Giannakoulis, A., Anson S., Watson, H., Hagen, K., Wadhwa, K., Müller, A., Begg, C., Doğulu, C., Karanci, N., Shreve, C.: D9.1 Design and specifications of the TACTIC online training and audit platform. Report of the TACTIC Project. European Dynamics SA, Athens, Hellas.
- Glik, D. C. (2007). Risk communication for public health emergencies. *Annu. Rev. Public Health*, 28, 33-54.
- Hagemeyer-Klose, M., & Wagner, K. (2009). Evaluation of flood hazard maps in print and web mapping services as information tools in flood risk communication. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 9(2), 563-574.
- Höppner, C., Buchecker, M., & Bründl, M. (2010). *Risk communication and natural hazards*. CapHaz project. Birmensdorf, Switzerland.
- Johnston, D., Paton, D., Crawford, G. L., Ronan, K., Houghton, B. and Bürgelt, P., (2005). Measuring tsunami preparedness in coastal Washington, United States. *Natural Hazards*. 35, pp.173-84.

- Kasperson, R. E., Renn, O., Slovic, P., Brown, H. S., Emel, J., Goble, R., Kasperson, J. X. & Ratick, S. (1988). The social amplification of risk: A conceptual framework. *Risk analysis*, 8(2), 177-187.
- Kuhlicke, C., Steinführer A., Begg, C. & Luther, L. (2012). Toward More Resilient Societies in the Field of Natural Hazards: CapHaz-Net's Lessons Learnt. CapHaz-Net WP10 Final Report, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ: Leipzig & Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute: Braunschweig (available at: www.caphaz-net.org).
- Kuhlicke, C., Begg, C., Müller, A., Karanci, N., Doğulu, C., Anson, S., Watson, H., Wadhwa, K., Konieczny, R., Walczykiewicz, T., Shreve, C. & C. Mante (2015). D11.5 Summarising report on the first rounds of case study workshops of the TACTIC project. Report of the TACTIC Project. Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Leipzig.
- Lundgren, R. E., & McMakin, A. H. (2013): *Risk communication: A handbook for communicating environmental, safety, and health risks*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Mileti, D. S., & Fitzpatrick, C. (1992). The causal sequence of risk communication in the Parkfield earthquake prediction experiment. *Risk Analysis*, 12(3), 393-400.
- Müller, A., Begg, C., Karanci, N., Giannakoulas, A., Anson, S., Watson, H., Wadhwa, K., Konieczny, R., Walczykiewicz, T., Mante, C. & C. Shreve (2015). D81. Outline of the long-term learning framework for a multi-hazard context. Report of the TACTIC Project. Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Leipzig.
- Morrow, B. H., (2009). Risk Behavior and Risk Communication: Synthesis and Expert Interviews. Final Report for the NOAA Coastal Services Center. [pdf] Available at:<<http://coast.noaa.gov/digitalcoast/sites/default/files/files/1366390027/risk-behavior-communication-report.pdf>>
- Nakagawa, Y., & Shaw, R. (2004). Social capital: A missing link to disaster recovery. *International Journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*, 22(1), 5-34.
- Otway, H., & Wynne, B. (1989). Risk communication: paradigm and paradox. *Risk Analysis*, 9(2), 141-145.
- Paton, D. (2008). Risk communication and natural hazard mitigation: how trust influences its effectiveness. *International Journal of Global Environmental Issues*, 8(1), 2-16.
- Paton, D., Okada, N. & Sagala, S. (2013). Understanding Preparedness for Natural Hazards: A cross cultural comparison, *Journal of Integrated Disaster Risk Management*, 3(1), 18-35.
- Pelling, M. (1999). The political ecology of flood hazard in urban Guyana. *Geoforum*, 30(3), 249-261.
- Pidgeon, N., Kasperson, R. E., & Slovic, P. (Eds.). (2003). *The social amplification of risk*. Cambridge University Press.
- Pulwarty, R. S., & Riebsame, W. E. (1997). The political ecology of vulnerability to hurricane-related hazards. In *Hurricanes* (pp. 185-214). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Renn, O. (1991) Risk communication and the social amplification of risk in: Kasperson, R. and Stallen (Eds) *Communicating Risks to the Public*, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Renn, O., Burns, W. J., Kasperson, J. X., Kasperson, R. E., & Slovic, P. (1992). The social amplification of risk: Theoretical foundations and empirical applications. *Journal of Social Issues*, 48(4), 137-160.

- Reynolds, B., & W. M. SEEGER (2005). Crisis and emergency risk communication as an integrative model. *Journal of health communication*, 10(1), 43-55.
- Scolobig, A., De Marchi, B., & Borga, M. (2012). The missing link between flood risk awareness and preparedness: findings from case studies in an Alpine Region. *Natural hazards*, 63(2), 499-520.
- Scolobig, A., Komendantova, N., Patt, A., Vichon C., Monfort, D., Begoubou-Valerius, M., Gasparini, P. & Ruocco, A. (2014). Multi-risk governance for natural hazards in Naples and Guadeloupe. *Natural Hazards* 73(3), 1523-1545.
- Shreve, C., Fordham, M., Anson, S., Watson, H., Hagen, K., Wadhwa, K., Begg, C., Müller, A., Kuhlicke, C., Karanci, N. (2014): *Report on risk perception and preparedness*, TACTIC project, North Umbria University, URL: http://www.tacticproject.eu/sites/default/files/images/resources-logo/Deliverable_D1.1_FINAL.pdf
- Siegrist, M., Cvetkovich, G., & Roth, C. (2000). Salient value similarity, social trust, and risk/benefit perception. *Risk analysis*, 20(3), 353-362.
- Slovic, P. (1987): Perception of risk, *Science*, 236(4799):280-285.
- Wachinger, G & Renn, O (2010): Risk Perception and Natural Hazards. CapHaz-Net WP3 Report, DIALOGIK Non-Profit Institute for Communication and Cooperative Research, Stuttgart (available at: http://caphaz-net.org/outcomes-results/CapHaz-Net_WP3_Risk-Perception.pdf).
- Wachinger G, Renn O, Begg C, Kuhlicke C, 2013, The risk perception paradox—implications for governance and communication of natural hazards. *Risk Analysis*. 33(6)1049 - 1065
- Walker G, Whittle R, Medd W, Watson N, 2010, *Risk governance and natural hazards*, CapHaz-Net WP2 report, Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, UK, <http://caphaz-net.org/outcomes-results>

Appendix